

ARTICLE TYPE

Resolving vibro-acoustics in poroelastic media via a multiscale virtual element method

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Abstract

We introduce a novel heterogeneous multi-scale method for the frequency response analysis of waves propagating in porous domains with a complex micro-structure. In this, the domain is decomposed onto polygonal coarse elements each clustering its local micro-structure. The micro-structure is resolved using the virtual element method hence providing ample flexibility into capturing fine scale heterogeneities of arbitrary polygonal shapes. The upscaling is performed through a set of numerically evaluated multi-scale basis functions. Rather than evaluating the basis for a broad band set of frequencies, a reduced order modelling approach is opted for. In this, the basis is evaluated for a select subset of frequencies, that is used as a basis for the evaluation of the remaining set through a proper orthogonal decomposition procedure. The solution of the coupled governing equations is then performed at the coarse-scale at a reduced computational cost. The performance of the method in terms of accuracy and computational efficiency is evaluated through a set of numerical examples for poro-elastic materials with heterogeneities of various shapes.

KEYWORDS:

Multiscale; Reduced Basis; Virtual Element Method; Porous media; Vibroacoustics; Biot

1 | INTRODUCTION

Multiscale processes are prevalent in nature, ranging from acoustic waves propagating in porous and fibrous domains^{1,2,3,4} to fractures propagating in composite materials⁵. Within this setting, developments in additive manufacturing yield components with detailed, tailor-made material layouts that are ready for wide-spread deployment in the automotive, aerospace and construction industries⁶. More specifically, materials such as foams and functionally graded composites can be designed to exhibit improved mechanical behaviour in comparison to metals or traditional composites; these involve larger strength to weight and damping to weight ratios⁷. However, the associated design process can prove costly as several iterations may be required to achieve a satisfactory blueprint. Hence, a genuine and urgent need is identified for simulation methods that can accelerate the design bottleneck without compromising on accuracy.

From a simulation standpoint, the ensuing exotic material layouts pose several challenges. The physics can, in principle, be described using the classical finite element method⁸. This however, would require highly refined meshes to resolve the heterogeneous morphologies at the meso-scale, thereby greatly increasing computational complexity⁹.

Multiscale modelling methods^{10,11,12} have been formulated to specifically address this limitation. They seek to drive down computational costs while retaining accuracy in the treatment of highly heterogeneous material profiles. To this end, homogenisation approaches are being used, see, e.g.,^{13,14,15} - including volume averaging and analytical homogenization¹⁶. These theories

rely on the assumptions of scale separation and periodicity. Such assumptions do not always hold true in highly heterogeneous domains. Hence, alternative methods have been developed, such as multiscale finite volume¹⁷, multiscale finite element methods (MsFEM)¹⁸, variational multiscale methods¹⁹, mortar multiscale methods²⁰, and heterogeneous multiscale methods²¹. A comparative discussion on different multiscale approaches in the context of elliptic problems was performed in^{22,23}.

20 Among these, the MsFEM has been shown to demonstrate favourable traits, particularly within the context of coupled problems. The technique was pioneered by^{24,25} and was extended to solve flow problems by²⁶ and later in^{27,28}. MsFEM relies on the definition of nested computational domains and involves the numerical evaluation of basis functions that map field variables, e.g. displacements, pressures etc. from the one to the other. A point of departure between the MsFEM and the popular FE² approach lies in the fine-scale description. In the FE², a fine-scale FE mesh is attached to each coarse scale integration point; conversely
25 in the MsFEM the coarse scale is fully spanned by the fine scale. Heterogeneous layouts where scales cannot be fully separated are hence more amenable to the MsFEM.²⁹ introduced the Enhanced/Extended Multiscale Finite Element Method (EMsFEM) to address elasto-statics by introducing additional meso-scale coupling terms into the multi-scale basis. Owing to the universality of the EMsFEM, from here on, the labels MsFEM and EMsFEM are used interchangeably to denote the Enhanced/Extended Multiscale Finite Element Method.

30 The Coupling Multiscale Finite Element Method (CMsFEM)³⁰ was developed to resolve the coupled field fully saturated porous media consolidation problem using a two-scale (meso-macro) approach. Mesoscale heterogeneities are mapped to the macroscopic scale using numerically computed multiscale basis functions. A thorough discussion on the computational gains of the MsFEM and the CMsFEM is provided in^{26,30,31}. A more specific comparison of different multiscale finite element approaches for composites and porous media flows was done in³².

35 Even though the evaluation of the multiscale basis is an offline procedure for the MsFEM, its computational cost can still be detrimental for the overall approach, especially in the case of highly heterogeneous domains. This becomes even more relevant in the case of vibroacoustics, where repeated evaluation of the multiscale basis functions at each frequency step is required. Other methods such as the mixed multiscale FEM³³, and multiscale finite volume method²⁸ also suffer from such a limitation.

40 Harnessing the power of reduced basis approximations, see, e.g.,^{34,35,36,37} introduced a Multiscale Reduced Basis Method (MsRBM) where a reduced order basis is generated offline at the coarse element level from a collection of high-fidelity solutions (often called snapshots). The Full Order Model (FOM), i.e., the discretized cell problem is then projected onto this reduced basis and a Reduced Order Model (ROM) of the original is simulated online to obtain the multiscale basis functions at a reduced cost. This approach, although extremely successful in accelerating MsFEM simulations has to this point only been used within the context of single phase elliptic problems.

45 There are significant difficulties experienced in applying MOR techniques to poroelastic materials³⁸. Owing to the strong coupling between the solid-skeleton and pore-fluid phases, and a low stiffness to weight ratio, a high modal density is experienced in the low frequency range. Consequently, modal-based MOR strategies as applied for the $\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{u}$ formulation in^{39,40} show that a large number of modes are required to retain accuracy. This effectively compromises the efficacy of the method⁴¹. A second bottleneck involves a treatment of the non-linear eigenvalue problems encountered when computing the reduced basis.
50 A complex modal approach was proposed in⁴², using a costly linearization strategy.

The above limitations in applying modal based MOR are addressed using a parametric model order reduction (pMOR) strategy for the $\mathbf{u} - p$ formulation in⁴³. This involves the identification of an optimal parametric manifold, wherein the optimal reduced basis varies in relation to the parameter under consideration (in this case, frequency)⁴⁴. A POD scheme is applied offline to extract this basis from the above mentioned snapshot matrix. In this work, we leverage the advantages of the pMOR and extend
55 the method to the case of wave propagation in poroelastic domains.

The standard MsFEM accounts for rectangular elements in the coarse scale and quadrilaterals in the fine scale; this limits the applicability of the method especially for the case of inclusions or voids of an arbitrary and typically non-convex geometry. In principle, one would be able to account for such heterogeneities via a very fine finite element discretization; this would considerably increase the number of elements to be resolved at the micro-scale hence countering the computational advantages of
60 the multiscale procedure. Optimization of the underlying mesh could thus prove critical to improving the performance of the method. Mesh optimization requires, as a prerequisite, numerical methods that allow for more flexible mesh generation capabilities. To achieve this, the Virtual Element Method (VEM) is employed to accurately and efficiently resolve the heterogeneities at the fine scale, as already done by the authors for elastostatic⁴⁵ and consolidation problems⁴⁶.

65 The VEM^{47,48,49} is a cutting-edge approach that provides ample flexibility in mesh generation by operating over polygonal, not necessarily convex, element topologies. The method avoids explicit expressions for its shape functions. Conversely, they are defined implicitly through carefully chosen degrees of freedom. The method has found widespread applications in topology

optimization⁵⁰, contact mechanics⁵¹, fracture^{52,53}, acoustical^{54,55} and flow problems^{56,57}. Mixed VEM^{49,58,59} allow applications in coupled poromechanical problems. In⁶⁰, the authors have investigated the merits of the VEM for vibro-acoustics but not within a multi-scale setting.

70 Using the methodology introduced by the authors in⁴⁶ for the case of static consolidation, in this work a fully coupled dynamic multi-scale virtual element method is introduced for vibro-acoustics over heterogeneous poro-elastic domains. The physics are described on the basis of a u - p formulation at the fine scale, and the corresponding fine to coarse scale projections are introduced. At the fine scale, the VEM is used to resolve local heterogeneities over complex material distributions and to evaluate the necessary multi-scale basis over the entire frequency spectrum. The most generic case of polygonal coarse element
75 topologies is considered and the corresponding upscaled state matrices are evaluated, i.e., the coarse scale mass and stiffness matrices for the solid phase, the compressibility and kinetic matrices for the fluid phase, and the associated coupling terms. Furthermore, a node insertion strategy at the coarse scale is developed and its merits vis-à-vis the resolution of the domain's dynamic response across the frequency spectrum are investigated and discussed. To further accelerate the computational scheme, the pMOR strategy is reformulated and originally upgraded for vibro-acoustics to eventually obtain a novel Coupled Multiscale
80 Reduced Basis Virtual Method (CMsRBVEM). Finally, the proposed CMsRBVEM is used to investigate the effect of periodic and a-periodic inclusions on the sound absorption capacities of porous materials widely used in the industry.

2 | PRELIMINARIES

2.1 | Strong form

A generalized 2-D poro-elastic domain as shown in Fig. 1 is given displacement and pressure (acoustic excitation) constraints $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$
85 and \bar{p} over Γ_u and Γ_p , respectively. Further, tractions and fluxes, $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{q}}$ are applied over Γ_t and Γ_q , respectively. The Dirichlet and Neumann boundaries are non-intersecting, i.e., $\Gamma_u \cap \Gamma_p = \emptyset$ and $\Gamma_t \cap \Gamma_q = \emptyset$.

Figure 1 A poro-elastic domain Ω with acoustical and mechanical excitations.

The response of the poro-elastic material to these vibro-acoustic excitations is described by the mixed $\mathbf{u} - p$ formulation⁶¹.

$$\operatorname{div}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s) + \omega^2 \tilde{\rho} \mathbf{u} = -\tilde{\gamma} \nabla p \quad - \text{solid phase}, \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{\Delta p}{\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}}} + \omega^2 \frac{p}{\tilde{K}_{\text{eq}}} = \omega^2 \tilde{\gamma} \operatorname{div}(\mathbf{u}) \quad - \text{fluid phase}, \quad (1b)$$

subject to the Dirichlet constraints on displacements and pressures,

$$\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} \text{ on } \Gamma_u, \quad p = \bar{p} e^{-j\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} \text{ on } \Gamma_p, \quad (2)$$

and the Neumann constraints on traction \mathbf{t} , and fluid flux \mathbf{q}

$$\mathbf{t} = \bar{\mathbf{t}} \text{ on } \Gamma_t, \quad \mathbf{q} = \bar{\mathbf{q}} \text{ on } \Gamma_q. \quad (3)$$

The excitation wave-number is contained in \mathbf{k} . A linear elasticity model is assumed for the solid-phase and uses the *in-vacuo* skeleton stress-tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s$. Structural damping is encapsulated here as well. The modified Biot density $\tilde{\rho}$ captures the dynamic behaviour associated with the skeleton. The visco-inertial and thermal dissipation, exhibited by the interaction between the pore-fluid and the complex inter-connected web of pore-networks is described by the dynamic mass density $\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}}$ and bulk modulus \tilde{K}_{eq} , respectively. The detailed constitutive models and associated material parameters used for each phase are detailed in Appendix A.

2.2 | VEM discretization

Introducing the finite dimensional approximations \mathbf{u}_h and p_h for the displacement and pressure fields, respectively and following a standard Galerkin procedure, the coupled strong form in Eq. (1) is discretized over a generalized fine-scale mesh, denoted by the label 'm'. An arbitrary element \mathcal{K}_m is selected from this mesh and visualized in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 An arbitrarily chosen polygonal element \mathcal{K}_m of order $k = 2$. It contains $n_V = 5$ corner, $n_V(k - 1) = 5$ interior edge and $k(k - 1)/2 = 1$ interior domain nodes.

The global matrix form of these equations at the fine-scale assume the following form

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{K} - \omega^2 \mathbf{M} & -\mathbf{C} \\ -\omega^2 \mathbf{C}^T & \mathbf{H} - \omega^2 \mathbf{Q} \end{Bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{u} \\ p \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{f}^u \\ \mathbf{f}^p \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the solid-phase elastic stiffness matrix, \mathbf{M} is the solid-phase mass matrix, \mathbf{H} is the fluid-phase kinetic matrix, \mathbf{Q} is the fluid-phase compressibility matrix, and \mathbf{C} is the phase-coupling matrix. Furthermore, \mathbf{f}^u and \mathbf{f}^p are the vectors nodal forces

and outflows, respectively. Finally, \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{p} are the nodal values of the corresponding finite dimensional approximations such that Eqs. (5) hold

$$\mathbf{u}_h = [\Phi_h^u]^T \mathbf{u}, \quad (5a)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_h = [\Phi_h^p]^T \mathbf{p}. \quad (5b)$$

In Eqs. (5), $[\Phi_h^u]$ and $[\Phi_h^p]$ collect the virtual element fine-scale canonical basis functions, respectively. Employing this ansatz over \mathcal{K}_m , the state-matrices can be assembled from their corresponding elementary contributions, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{K}_m = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s(\Phi_h^u) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s(\Phi_h^u) d\Omega, \quad (6)$$

and

$$\mathbf{M}_m = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \Phi_h^u \cdot \Phi_h^u d\Omega, \quad (7)$$

for the solid-phase elastic stiffness and mass matrices,

$$\mathbf{H}_m = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \nabla(\Phi_h^p) \cdot \nabla(\Phi_h^p) d\Omega, \quad (8)$$

and

$$\mathbf{Q}_m = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \Phi_h^p \cdot \Phi_h^p d\Omega, \quad (9)$$

for the fluid-phase kinetic matrix and compressibility matrices, and

$$\mathbf{C}_m = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \Phi_h^p \cdot \Phi_h^u d\Omega, \quad (10)$$

for the phase-coupling matrix. The force \mathbf{f}_m^u and acoustic excitation \mathbf{f}_m^p vectors naturally arise from the imposed Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions shown in Fig. 1; explicit derivations are provided in⁶⁰.

To evaluate the state matrices in Eqs. (6)-(10), the canonical shape-functions Φ_h^u , Φ_h^p and their associated spaces \mathcal{V}_h^u , \mathcal{V}_{ah}^p have to be defined. For the case of a k_{th} order VEM, these spaces are defined as

$$\mathcal{V}_h^u = [\mathcal{W}_h]^d, \quad d = 2, \quad \mathcal{V}_h^p = [\mathcal{W}_h]^d, \quad d = 1, \quad (11a)$$

$$\mathcal{W}_h = \{v \in [\mathcal{H}^1(\Omega) \cap C^0(\mathcal{K}_m)] : v|_{\mathcal{K}_m} \in \mathcal{V}_h^{\mathcal{K}}, \forall \mathcal{K}_m\},$$

and $\mathcal{V}_h^{\mathcal{K}}$ has the following definition:

$$\mathcal{V}_h^{\mathcal{K}} = \{v \in [\mathcal{H}^1(\mathcal{K}_m) \cap C^0(\mathcal{K}_m)] : v_{,i}|_e \in \mathbb{P}_k(e) \forall e \in \partial\mathcal{K}_m ; \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta v_{,i}|_{\mathcal{K}_m} \in \mathbb{P}_{k-2}(\mathcal{K}_m), \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, d\},$$

The space \mathbb{P}_k in Eq. (12) denotes a k_{th} order polynomial space.

Members of these spaces lack an explicit definition over the fine-element interior, where complicated non-polynomial forms can be assumed. Rather, they are implicitly defined through the DoFs provided in Table 1 and Table 2 for the displacement and pressure fields, respectively. As a result, one cannot directly operate on Φ_h^u and Φ_h^p . To this end, the fields are split into polynomial and non-polynomial components

$$\Phi_h^u = \Phi_h^{u,\pi} + (\Phi_h^u - \Phi_h^{u,\pi}), \quad (13a)$$

$$\Phi_h^p = \Phi_h^{p,\pi} + (\Phi_h^p - \Phi_h^{p,\pi}). \quad (13b)$$

Table 1 Displacement Degrees of Freedom for $\mathcal{V}_h^u(\mathcal{K}_m)$. For Area moments, the monomials belong to the $[\mathbb{M}_{k-2}(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2$ space.

DoF Type	Number of DoFs n_{DOF}^u	Description
Corner	$N_C^u = 2n_V$	$\mathbf{u}_h(\mathbf{x}_j)$, $j = 1, \dots, n_V$
Edge	$N_E^u = 2n_V(k-1)$	$\mathbf{u}_h(\mathbf{x}_j^e)$, $j = 1, \dots, k-1$ for each edge
Area Moment	$N_A^u = 2 \frac{k(k-1)}{2}$	$\frac{1}{ \mathcal{K} } \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \mathbf{u}_h \cdot \mathbf{m} \, d\mathcal{K}$ $\forall \mathbf{m} \in [\mathbb{M}_{k-2}(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2$

105 To compute the polynomial components, the à priori unknown operator-specific projectors, $\Phi_h^{u,\pi} \equiv \Pi_k^\epsilon \Phi_h^u$ and $\Phi_h^{p,\pi} \equiv \Pi_k^{\nabla p} \Phi_h^p$ are introduced. These projectors map the polynomial components onto the polynomial spaces $[\mathbb{P}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2$ and $\mathbb{P}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)$, respectively. For the sake of completeness, explicit expressions are provided in Section B.1 of the Appendix.

Inserting Eqs. (13) into Eqs. (6) and (8) and performing the necessary algebraic manipulations, the resulting VEM expressions for the stiffness and the kinetic matrix assume the following form

$$\mathbf{K}_m = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \sigma_s(\Pi_k^\epsilon \Phi_h^u) : \epsilon_s(\Pi_k^\epsilon \Phi_h^u) + \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \sigma_s(\Phi_h^u - \Pi_k^\epsilon \Phi_h^u) : \epsilon_s(\Phi_h^u - \Pi_k^\epsilon \Phi_h^u), \quad (14)$$

and

$$\mathbf{H}_m = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \nabla(\Pi_k^{\nabla p} \Phi_h^p) \cdot \nabla(\Pi_k^{\nabla p} \Phi_h^p) + \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \nabla(\Phi_h^p - \Pi_k^{\nabla p} \Phi_h^p) \cdot \nabla(\Phi_h^p - \Pi_k^{\nabla p} \Phi_h^p), \quad (15)$$

repectively.

The first set of terms on the right hand side are called *consistency terms* and are exactly computable. Conversely, the second set of terms contain the unknown quantities Φ_h^u and Φ_h^p and cannot be evaluated in their current form. Alternately, one seeks easy-to-compute approximations called *stability terms*. Consequently, the approximations now read

$$\mathbf{K}_m \approx \mathbf{K}_{m,C} + \mathbf{K}_{m,S}, \quad (16)$$

and

$$\mathbf{H}_m \approx \mathbf{H}_{m,C} + \mathbf{H}_{m,S}. \quad (17)$$

110 The consistency matrices $\mathbf{K}_{m,C}$ and $\mathbf{H}_{m,C}$ and stability matrices $\mathbf{K}_{m,S}$ and $\mathbf{H}_{m,S}$ are provided in Appendix B. The remaining VEM matrices are obtained in an identical fashion.

Remark 1. It is to be noted that Eqs. (4) as presented is not a symmetric matrix. To facilitate efficient iterative solvers, symmetricity is restored by dividing the second row-block of matrices by ω^2 .

3 | MULTISCALE VIRTUAL ELEMENTS FOR VIBRO-ACOUSTICS

3.1 | Overview

At the first level of the two-scale approximation investigated herein, the domain is decomposed onto a coarse-mesh, see also Fig. 3(a). To this end, an approximation, $\Omega_H \approx \Omega$ is considered that discretizes the domain with n_M nodes and $n_{M_{\text{el}}}$ non-intersecting polygonal coarse elements of maximum diameter H , i.e.,

$$\Omega_H = \bigcup_{\alpha=1}^{n_{M_{\text{el}}}} \mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}. \quad (18)$$

Table 2 Pressure Degrees of Freedom for $\mathcal{V}_h^p(\mathcal{K}_m)$. For Area moments, the monomials belong to the $\mathbb{M}_{k-2}(\mathcal{K}_m)$ space.

DoF Type	Number of DoFs n_{DOF}^p	Description
Corner	$N_C^p = n_V$	$p_h(\mathbf{x}_j),$ $j = 1, \dots, n_V$
Edge	$N_E^p = n_V(k-1)$	$p_h(\mathbf{x}_j^e),$ $j = 1, \dots, k-1$ for each edge
Area Moment	$N_A^p = \frac{k(k-1)}{2}$	$\frac{1}{ \mathcal{K} } \int_{\mathcal{K}_{m(i)}^\alpha} p_h \cdot \mathbf{m} \, d\mathcal{K}$ $\forall \mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{M}_{k-2}(\mathcal{K}_m)$

	Corner Nodes	Edge Nodes
$\mathcal{K}_{M(4)}$	$\mathbf{X}_C^4 = [\mathbf{X}_1^4, \mathbf{X}_2^4, \mathbf{X}_3^4, \mathbf{X}_4^4, \mathbf{X}_5^4, \mathbf{X}_6^4, \mathbf{X}_7^4]$	$\mathbf{X}_E^4 = [\mathbf{X}_8^4, \mathbf{X}_9^4, \mathbf{X}_{10}^4, \mathbf{X}_{11}^4, \mathbf{X}_{12}^4, \mathbf{X}_{13}^4, \mathbf{X}_{14}^4]$
$\mathcal{K}_{m(9)}^4$	$\mathbf{x}_c^{4,9} = [\mathbf{x}_1^{4,9}, \mathbf{x}_2^{4,9}, \mathbf{x}_3^{4,9}, \mathbf{x}_4^{4,9}, \mathbf{x}_5^{4,9}]$	$\mathbf{x}_e^{4,9} = [\mathbf{x}_6^{4,9}, \mathbf{x}_7^{4,9}, \mathbf{x}_8^{4,9}, \mathbf{x}_9^{4,9}, \mathbf{x}_{10}^{4,9}]$

Table 3 Corner and edge nodes for coarse-element $\mathcal{K}_{M(4)}$ and fine-element $\mathcal{K}_{m(9)}^4$ as illustrated in Fig. 3.

Each polygonal coarse element α comprises n_C^α corner nodes and n_E^α edge nodes (Fig. 3(b)). Consequently, the total number of coarse nodes associated with $\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}$ reads $n_M^\alpha = n_C^\alpha + n_E^\alpha$. The coarse scale nodal displacement and pressure vectors associated with the coarse element α are defined as $\mathbf{u}_{M(\alpha)}$ and $\mathbf{p}_{M(\alpha)}$, respectively.

At the second level, each polygonal coarse element $\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}$, $\alpha = 1, \dots, n_{M_{\text{el}}}$ clusters a fine scale virtual element mesh with n_m^α fine-scale nodes and $n_{m_{\text{el}}}^\alpha$ non-overlapping polygonal fine-scale virtual elements of maximum diameter h (Fig. 3(b)-(c))

$$\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)} = \bigcup_{i=1}^{n_{m_{\text{el}}}^\alpha} \mathcal{K}_{m(i)}^\alpha, \quad \forall 1 \leq \alpha \leq n_{M_{\text{el}}}. \quad (19)$$

The corresponding fine scale nodal vectors of displacement and pressure are defined as \mathbf{u}_m^i and \mathbf{p}_m^i , respectively. Finally, \mathbf{u}_m and \mathbf{p}_m denote the $(2n_m^\alpha \times 1)$ vector of fine scale nodal displacements and the $(n_m^\alpha \times 1)$ vector of nodal pressures of the α^{th} coarse element.

We emphasize that the fine-scale discretization is local to the coarse element and that the solution of the resulting discretized governing equations is performed at the coarse element mesh. The fine scale discretization of the coarse element is commonly referred to in the MsFEM community as a Representative Volume Element (or RVE). This should not be confused with the typical concept of an RVE that is central to computational homogenization theories and where scale separation is implied.

3.2 | Micro to macro mapping

The unknown field variables, i.e., displacements \mathbf{u} and pressures p are approximated at the coarse-scale with the finite dimensional approximations \mathbf{u}_H and p_H , respectively, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{u}_H \approx \mathbf{u}, \quad \delta \mathbf{u}_H \approx \delta \mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{V}_H^u \subset \mathcal{V}^u \equiv [\mathcal{H}^1(\Omega_H)]^2, \quad (20a)$$

$$p_H \approx p, \quad \delta p_H \approx \delta p \in \mathcal{V}_H^p \subset \mathcal{V}^p \equiv [\mathcal{H}^1(\Omega_H)], \quad (20b)$$

where $\delta \mathbf{u}_H$ and δp_H denote variations of their corresponding fields. Furthermore, $[\mathcal{H}^1(\Omega_H)]^2$ and $\mathcal{H}^1(\Omega_H)$ represent 2-D and 1-D Hilbert spaces, respectively.

Figure 3 A fidget-spinner shaped poroelastic domain with highly heterogeneous static airflow resistivity sampled from a log-normal distribution ($\mu = 6, \sigma = 24$). (a) Coarse-scale CVT mesh containing $n_M = 205$ nodes and $n_{M_{el}} = 75$ elements. (b) Example coarse-element $\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}$, $\alpha = 4$ of order $k = 2$ with $n_M^4 = 14$ coarse-nodes and $n_E^4 = 7$ edges. The coarse element has a fine-scale CVT mesh containing $n_m^4 = 202$ nodes and $n_{e_{el}}^4 = 100$ elements. (c) Example fine-element $\mathcal{K}_{m(i)}^4$, $i = 9$ of order $k = 2$ with $n_m^{4,9} = 11$ fine-nodes and $n_e^{4,9} = 5$ edges. The corner and edge nodes associated with these configurations are collected in Table 3.

The coarse solution spaces \mathcal{V}_H^u and \mathcal{V}_H^p are defined as

$$\mathcal{V}_H^u = \text{span}\{\alpha(\phi_H^u)_\beta : 1 \leq \alpha \leq n_{M_{el}}, 1 \leq \beta \leq n_M^\alpha\}, \quad (21a)$$

$$\mathcal{V}_H^p = \text{span}\{\alpha(\phi_H^p)_\beta : 1 \leq \alpha \leq n_{M_{el}}, 1 \leq \beta \leq n_M^\alpha\}, \quad (21b)$$

where $\alpha(\phi_H^u)_\beta$ and $\alpha(\phi_H^p)_\beta$ are multiscale basis functions that define a partition of unity over the coarse element α , i.e.,

$$\alpha(\phi_H^u)_\beta \Big|_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_\gamma^\alpha} = \alpha(\phi_H^p)_\beta \Big|_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_\gamma^\alpha} = \delta_{\beta\gamma}, \quad 1 \leq \gamma \leq n_M^\alpha, \quad (22a)$$

$$\sum_{\beta=1}^{n_M^\alpha} \alpha(\phi_H^u)_\beta = \sum_{\beta=1}^{n_M^\alpha} \alpha(\phi_H^p)_\beta = 1. \quad (22b)$$

Using the basis introduced in Eqs. (22), the nodal information associated with fine-element $\mathcal{K}_{m(i)}$ can be interpolated at the relevant coarse-element $\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}$. More concretely, the displacements $\mathbf{u}_{m(i)}^\alpha$ and pressures $\mathbf{p}_{m(i)}^\alpha$ have the forms

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_{m(i)}^\alpha &= {}^\alpha \Phi_{H,m(i)}^u \mathbf{u}_{M(\alpha)}, \\ \mathbf{p}_{m(i)}^\alpha &= {}^\alpha \Phi_{H,m(i)}^p \mathbf{p}_{M(\alpha)}, \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

130 where the arrays ${}^\alpha \Phi_{H,m(i)}^u$ and ${}^\alpha \Phi_{H,m(i)}^p$ denote multiscale basis functions mapping quantities between the $\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}$'s coarse-nodes and $\mathcal{K}_{m(i)}^\alpha$'s fine-nodes.

Collecting contributions from each fine-element, Eq. (23) is expressed over the entire RVE

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_m^\alpha &= {}^\alpha \Phi_H^u \mathbf{u}_M^\alpha, \\ \mathbf{p}_m^\alpha &= {}^\alpha \Phi_H^p \mathbf{p}_M^\alpha, \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where the arrays ${}^\alpha\Phi_H^u$ and ${}^\alpha\Phi_H^p$ collect the coarse element multiscale basis functions corresponding to each coarse node degree of freedom and assume the following form

$$\begin{aligned} {}^\alpha\Phi_H^u &= [(\phi_H^u)_1 \dots (\phi_H^u)_\beta \dots (\phi_H^u)_{n_M^\alpha}] \\ {}^\alpha\Phi_H^p &= [(\phi_H^p)_1 \dots (\phi_H^p)_\beta \dots (\phi_H^p)_{n_M^\alpha}] \end{aligned}, \quad 1 < \beta < n_M^\alpha, \quad (25)$$

for the displacement and pressure fields, respectively. The index α is dropped from the vector components of the multiscale basis arrays in Eqs. (25) for brevity.

3.3 | Evaluation of the multi-scale basis functions

The vectors of the multi-scale basis functions $(\phi_H^u)_\beta$ correspond to the static deformation modes of \mathcal{K}_M . These are numerically evaluated through the following homogeneous boundary value problem, which is obtained from the static form of Eq. (1a) over the coarse domain \mathcal{K}_M , i.e.,

$$\begin{cases} \operatorname{div}(\sigma_s((\phi_H^u)_\beta)) = 0, & \text{in } \mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \\ (\phi_H^u)_\beta = (\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta, & \text{on } \partial\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \end{cases}, \quad 1 \leq \beta \leq n_M^\alpha, \quad (26)$$

135 where $(\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta$ correspond to appropriate Dirichlet constraints defined over the coarse element boundary $\partial\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}$ such that global displacement conformity is ensured.

Since the boundary value problem of Eq. (26) is defined over the coarse element domain only, this is discretized using the fine scale mesh associated with each coarse element separately. In this work, we leverage the flexibility of the VEM and discretize Eq. (26) over polytope elements as discussed in Section 2.2.

Hence, Eq. (26) is recast into the associated matrix form

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{K}_m^\alpha(\phi_H^u)_\beta = 0, \\ (\phi_H^u)_\beta = (\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta, & \text{on } \partial\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \end{cases}, \quad 1 \leq \beta \leq n_M^\alpha, \quad (27)$$

140 where \mathbf{K}_m^α is the α_{th} coarse element *elastic-stiffness* matrix. This is assembled via a typical assembly operator from localised fine scale virtual element contributions as discussed in Section 2.2.

Similarly, the basis $(\phi_H^p)_\beta$ corresponds to the static acoustical modes of $\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}$. These are evaluated through the homogeneous boundary value problem of Eq. (28), which is obtained from the static form of Eq. (1b)

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_{\text{eq}}} \Delta(\phi_H^p)_\beta = 0, & \text{in } \mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \\ (\phi_H^p)_\beta = (\overline{\phi_H^p})_\beta, & \text{on } \partial\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \end{cases}, \quad 1 \leq \beta \leq n_M^\alpha, \quad (28)$$

where $(\overline{\phi_H^p})_\beta$ are the corresponding pressure-field Dirichlet boundary conditions. The matrix form associated with Eq. (28) is

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{H}_m^\alpha(\phi_H^p)_\beta = 0, \\ (\phi_H^p)_\beta = (\overline{\phi_H^p})_\beta, & \text{on } \partial\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \end{cases}, \quad 1 \leq \beta \leq n_M^\alpha, \quad (29)$$

where \mathbf{H}_m^α is the *fluid-kinetic* matrix, assembled from the fine scale virtual element contributions (see Eq. (8)) over the coarse element domain.

145 **Remark 2.** The evaluation of the multi-scale basis functions is performed for each coarse element separately. Hence, it involves the solution of a boundary value problem of an order significantly lower than that of the initial problem. Furthermore, each problem is independent and the evaluation of the basis for all coarse elements can be performed in parallel. Clearly, the computational complexity is further reduced if coarse elements have identical micro-structures.

150 **Remark 3.** We note that it is not necessary for the edge nodes of the coarse mesh to coincide with corner (or edge) nodes of the micro-mesh. Eqs. (27) are solved as long as a proper set of boundary conditions is established at the coarse mesh that complies with the requirements set by Eqs. (22). However, we find that using coincident macro and micro nodes is a reasonable option as

it simplifies mesh generation. In particular, a fine scale mesh can be generated and then clusters of the existing micro nodes can be selected to serve as coarse nodes based on adhoc criteria .

3.4 | Coarse element Dirichlet boundary conditions

Figure 4 Linear kinematical constraints are imposed over two adjacent faces of the coarse element under consideration. The fine-nodes corresponding to the remaining edges are fixed.

The assumption on the Dirichlet constraints $(\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta$ and $(\overline{\phi_H^p})_\beta$ is crucial for the accuracy of the method. Typical choices involve linear, periodic and oversampled conditions, see, e.g.⁶². An example of imposing linear kinematical constraints is illustrated in Fig. 4. In the context of unstructured coarse grids employed in this work, the notion of periodicity breaks down. Furthermore, the precise nature of oversampled domains is not amenable to a rigorous definition in this case. Linear boundary conditions, while general enough to accommodate polygonal coarse element geometries, are unable to accurately capture physical modes in coarse elements with highly oscillating material coefficients.

To this end, multi-node coarse elements with generalized K_{th} order polynomial profiles over the relevant edges $E_\beta^\alpha \in \partial\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}$, $1 \leq \beta \leq n_M^\alpha$ have been shown to provide well-behaved micro to macro mappings⁶³. For the case of the displacement field, the following boundary condition profiles are defined for the multiscale basis functions associated with corner coarse-nodes \mathbf{x}_C .

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta \Big|_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_\beta} &= 1, \forall \mathbf{x}_\beta \in \mathbf{x}_C, \\
 \begin{cases} (\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta \Big|_{\forall \mathbf{x} \in E_{\beta_1}} &= \chi_\beta^u \Big|_{\forall \mathbf{x} \in E_{\beta_1}}, \\ (\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta \Big|_{\forall \mathbf{x} \in E_{\beta_2}} &= \chi_\beta^u \Big|_{\forall \mathbf{x} \in E_{\beta_2}}, \end{cases} \text{ if } \mathbf{x}_\beta = E_{\beta_1} \cap E_{\beta_2}, \\
 (\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta \Big|_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_\beta} &= 0, \text{ otherwise.}
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Furthermore, the boundary conditions for the evaluation of the multiscale basis functions associated with the edge coarse-nodes \mathbf{x}_E become

$$\begin{aligned} (\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta \Big|_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_\beta} &= 1, & \forall \mathbf{x}_\beta \in \mathbf{x}_E, \\ (\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta \Big|_{\forall \mathbf{x} \in E_\beta} &= \chi_\beta^u(E_\beta), \\ (\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta &= \mathbf{0}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

160 where $\chi_\beta^u = \mathbb{P}_K(E_\beta)$ represents a K_{th} order polynomial profile over the edge E_β . Similar expressions are defined for the case of the pressure field.

Although the profiles introduced in Eqs. (30)-(31) allow for enhanced flexibility, these still do not faithfully capture the behaviour induced by underlying heterogeneities. In this work, oscillating boundary conditions are used to retrieve exact boundary profiles by solving a reduced analogue of Eqs. (27) and (29) over each boundary E_β of the coarse element, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{K}_m^\alpha \chi_\beta^u = 0, \quad \text{over } E_\beta, \quad (32)$$

and

$$\mathbf{H}_m^\alpha \chi_\beta^p = 0, \quad \text{over } E_\beta, \quad (33)$$

for the displacement and pressure fields, respectively. We show in⁴⁶ that in the case of such highly heterogeneous problems, bases obtained with oscillating constraints offer higher accuracies without compromising efficiency. The multiscale basis function $(\phi_H^p)_\beta$, $\alpha = 4$, $\beta = 1$ at $f = 20$ kHz, as evaluated by the VEM for both choices of boundary constraints is illustrated in Fig. 5.

165 Note that a significant relative difference of 58.35% is observed between the resultant bases.

4 | REDUCED ORDER BASIS FUNCTIONS

The quantities ${}^\alpha(\phi_H^u)_\beta$ and ${}^\alpha(\phi_H^p)_\beta$ need to be repeatedly evaluated for each frequency step to account for spectral variability of the underlying material configuration.

Global reduced-basis spaces of equal dimension $(\mathcal{V}_H^u)_{n_{RB}^u} \approx \mathcal{V}_H^u$, $(\mathcal{V}_H^p)_{n_{RB}^p} \approx \mathcal{V}_H^p$ are defined

$$(\mathcal{V}_H^u)_{n_{RB}^u} = \text{span}\{ {}^\alpha(\tilde{\phi}_H^u)_\beta : 1 \leq \alpha \leq n_{M_{el}}, 1 \leq \beta \leq n_M^\alpha \}, \quad (34a)$$

$$(\mathcal{V}_H^p)_{n_{RB}^p} = \text{span}\{ {}^\alpha(\tilde{\phi}_H^p)_\beta : 1 \leq \alpha \leq n_{M_{el}}, 1 \leq \beta \leq n_M^\alpha \}, \quad (34b)$$

where ${}^\alpha(\tilde{\phi}_H^u)_\beta$ and ${}^\alpha(\tilde{\phi}_H^p)_\beta$ are reduced-basis multiscale basis functions also enjoying the properties in Eq. (22).

The arrays ${}^\alpha\tilde{\Phi}_H^u$ and ${}^\alpha\tilde{\Phi}_H^p$ collect the individual reduced bases analogous to Eqs. (25)

$$\begin{aligned} {}^\alpha\tilde{\Phi}_H^u &= [(\tilde{\phi}_H^u)_1 \dots (\tilde{\phi}_H^u)_\beta \dots (\tilde{\phi}_H^u)_{n_M^\alpha}] \\ {}^\alpha\tilde{\Phi}_H^p &= [(\tilde{\phi}_H^p)_1 \dots (\tilde{\phi}_H^p)_\beta \dots (\tilde{\phi}_H^p)_{n_M^\alpha}] \end{aligned}, \quad 1 < \beta < n_M^\alpha. \quad (35)$$

These basis functions are obtained by solving the following cell problems

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_m^\alpha(\tilde{\Phi}_H^u)_\beta = \mathbf{0}, & \text{on } \mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \\ (\tilde{\Phi}_H^u)_\beta = (\overline{\phi_H^u})_\beta, & \text{on } \partial\mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

and

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_m^\alpha(\tilde{\Phi}_H^p)_\beta = \mathbf{0}, & \text{on } \mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \\ (\tilde{\Phi}_H^p)_\beta = (\overline{\phi_H^p})_\beta, & \text{on } \partial\mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

Figure 5 Multiscale basis function $(\phi_H^p)_{4,1}$ computed with (a) polynomial constraints $\chi_{4,1}^u(E_1^4) = \mathbb{P}_2(E_1^4)$ and $\chi_{4,1}^u(E_7^4) = \mathbb{P}_2(E_7^4)$, and (b) oscillating constraints computed from Eqs. (32)-(33).

where $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_m^\alpha$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_m^\alpha$ are reduced order representations of \mathbf{K}_m^α and \mathbf{H}_m^α , respectively, and are obtained by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_m^\alpha = \tilde{\Phi}_h^{u,T} \mathbf{K}_m^\alpha \tilde{\Phi}_h^u, \quad (38a)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_m^\alpha = \tilde{\Phi}_h^{p,T} \mathbf{H}_m^\alpha \tilde{\Phi}_h^p, \quad (38b)$$

170 where $\tilde{\Phi}_h^u = [\tilde{\phi}_{h1}^u, \dots, \tilde{\phi}_{h n_{\text{RB}}^u}^u]$ and $\tilde{\Phi}_h^p = [\tilde{\phi}_{h1}^p, \dots, \tilde{\phi}_{h n_{\text{RB}}^p}^p]$ project quantities onto these reduced-basis spaces. They are obtained from a Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD).

These POD bases are generated by the *method of snapshots*. A snapshot matrix is defined for the solid-phase to this end

$$\underbrace{\mathbf{S}^u}_{(2n_m^\alpha \times n_s^u)} = \left[\mathbf{u}_h(\omega_1^s), \dots, \mathbf{u}_h(\omega_{n_s^u}^s) \right], \quad (39)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_h(\omega_i^s)$, $1 \leq i \leq n_s^u$ denote displacement snapshots, i.e., high-fidelity fine-scale solutions evaluated according to Eq. (27), at a sampled frequency ω_i^s .

A Singular Valued Decomposition (SVD) is now applied

$$\mathbf{S}^u = \underbrace{\mathbf{L}^u}_{(2n_m^\alpha \times 2n_m^\alpha)} \underbrace{\mathbf{\Sigma}^u}_{(2n_m^\alpha \times n_s^u)} \underbrace{\mathbf{R}^u}_{(n_s^u \times n_s^u)}, \quad (40)$$

175 where \mathbf{L}^u and \mathbf{R}^u contain left and right singular displacement vectors, respectively. $\mathbf{\Sigma}^u$ contains singular values σ_i^u , $1 \leq i \leq n_s^u$ along its diagonal in descending order of magnitude. Each singular value can be associated with its corresponding left and right singular vectors. The POD bases $\tilde{\Phi}^u$ is obtained from a truncation of \mathbf{L}^u according to the criterion $\frac{(\sigma_i^u)^2}{(\sigma_1^u)^2} > \epsilon$, where ϵ is an error tolerance. The associated singular value decay is illustrated in Fig. 6. A sharp change in the decay rate is observed at a singular value ratio of 10^{-16} . Consequently, the truncation tolerance is set at $\epsilon_\sigma = 10^{-16}$

Figure 6 Decay of the first $n_s^u = 15$ singular values computed for the snapshot matrix \mathbf{S}^u . The horizontal black dashed line indicates the truncation tolerance.

Similarly, the snapshot matrix for the fluid-phase is provided

$$\underbrace{\mathbf{S}^p}_{(n_m^\alpha \times n_s^p)} = \left[\mathbf{p}_h(\omega_1^s), \dots, \mathbf{p}_h(\omega_{n_s^p}^s) \right], \quad (41)$$

180 where $\mathbf{p}_h(\omega_i^s)$, $1 \leq i \leq n_s^p$ represent pressure snapshots computed with Eq. (29). The SVD is performed on \mathbf{S}^p analogous to Eq. (40) and the truncated POD basis $\tilde{\Phi}^p$ is obtained by observing the corresponding singular value decay rule.

185 **Remark 4.** The accuracy of model order reduction depends largely on the quality of the snapshot matrix \mathbf{S}^u and \mathbf{S}^p . Generating FOM snapshots is typically the primary bottleneck in the method, since large high fidelity matrices need to be inverted (or iteratively solved). To this end, sampling strategies play a vital role in determining computational efficiency. Quasi random sampling (Monte-Carlo or Latin Hypercube methods) is recommended over brute force tensorial approaches, see, e.g., the discussion provided in⁴⁴. The SVD factorization can prove expensive for large snapshot matrices, especially e.g., when $n_s^u \gg n_m^\alpha$. However, in most cases since $n_s^u \ll n_m^\alpha$, the cost of employing the SVD is justified.

The complete full order bases $(\phi_H^u)_{\alpha\beta}$ and $(\phi_H^p)_{\alpha\beta}$ are now retrieved at reduced computational cost

$$\alpha(\phi_H^u)_\beta = \tilde{\Phi}_h^u \alpha(\tilde{\Phi}_H^u)_\beta, \quad (42a)$$

$$\alpha(\phi_H^p)_\beta = \tilde{\Phi}_h^p \alpha(\tilde{\Phi}_H^p)_\beta. \quad (42b)$$

The procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Multiscale basis function evaluation schema using the pMOR.

Data: Define coarse mesh and fine mesh/micromesh and material properties

foreach coarse element α **do**

Assemble \mathbf{K}_m^α ;

foreach macro-node $\beta = 1, \dots, n_M^\alpha$ **do**

foreach macro degree of freedom **do**

Define $(\Phi_H^u)_\beta$;

foreach sampled frequency $\omega_k, k = 1, \dots, n_s$ **do**

$$\text{Solve: } \begin{cases} \mathbf{K}_m^\alpha(\omega_k)(\Phi_H^u)_\beta(\omega_k) = \mathbf{0} \\ (\Phi_H^u)_\beta = \overline{(\Phi_H^u)_\beta}, \text{ on } \partial\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)} \end{cases} \quad \text{Assemble to } \mathbf{S}_u^\alpha$$

Get $\tilde{\Phi}_h^u$ from \mathbf{S}_u^α (SVD and truncation);

foreach remaining frequency step $\omega_k, k = 1, \dots, n_{freq} - n_s$ **do**

$$\text{Solve ROM: } \begin{cases} \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_m^\alpha(\omega_k)(\tilde{\Phi}_H^u)_\beta(\omega_k) = \mathbf{0} \\ (\tilde{\Phi}_H^u)_\beta = \overline{(\tilde{\Phi}_H^u)_\beta}, \text{ on } \partial\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)} \end{cases}$$

Get FOM solution: $(\phi_H^u)_\beta(\omega_k) = \tilde{\Phi}_h^u(\tilde{\Phi}_H^u)_\beta(\omega_k)$

Assemble \mathbf{H}_m^α ;

foreach macro-node $\beta = 1, \dots, n_M^\alpha$ **do**

foreach macro degree of freedom **do**

Define $(\Phi_H^p)_\beta$;

foreach sampled frequency $\omega_k, k = 1, \dots, n_s$ **do**

$$\text{Solve: } \begin{cases} \mathbf{H}_m^\alpha(\omega_k)(\Phi_H^p)_\beta(\omega_k) = \mathbf{0} \\ (\Phi_H^p)_\beta = \overline{(\Phi_H^p)_\beta}, \text{ on } \partial\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)} \end{cases} \quad \text{Assemble to } \mathbf{S}_p^\alpha$$

Get $\tilde{\Phi}_h^p$ from \mathbf{S}_p^α (SVD and truncation);

foreach remaining frequency step $\omega_k, k = 1, \dots, n_{freq} - n_s$ **do**

$$\text{Solve ROM: } \begin{cases} \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_m^\alpha(\omega_k)(\tilde{\Phi}_H^p)_\beta(\omega_k) = \mathbf{0} \\ (\tilde{\Phi}_H^p)_\beta = \overline{(\tilde{\Phi}_H^p)_\beta}, \text{ on } \partial\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)} \end{cases}$$

Get FOM solution: $(\phi_H^p)_\beta(\omega_k) = \tilde{\Phi}_h^p(\tilde{\Phi}_H^p)_\beta(\omega_k)$

5 | UPSCALING AND SOLUTION PROCEDURE

The matrix form of Eq. (1) for each frequency step ω_k are expressed for a single fine-scale element as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{m(i)}^\alpha - \omega_k^2 \mathbf{M}_{m(i)}^\alpha & -\mathbf{C}_{m(i)}^\alpha \\ -\omega_k^2 \mathbf{C}_{m(i)}^{\alpha T} & \mathbf{H}_{m(i)}^\alpha - \omega_k^2 \mathbf{Q}_{m(i)}^\alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_m^\alpha \\ \mathbf{p}_m^\alpha \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_{m(i)}^{u,\alpha} \\ \mathbf{f}_{m(i)}^{p,\alpha} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (43)$$

where the state matrices $\mathbf{K}_{m(i)}^\alpha$ and $\mathbf{H}_{m(i)}^\alpha$, $\mathbf{Q}_{m(i)}^\alpha$, and $\mathbf{C}_{m(i)}^\alpha$ are evaluated using the VEM according to the procedure discussed in Section 2.2.

Substituting the micro to macro mapping relations from Eq. (23) into Eq. (43), and pre-multiplying the first row-set of equations by $\Phi_{H,m}^{u T}$, and second row-set of equations by $\Phi_{H,m}^{p T}$, the following equation is obtained (it is to be noted that the individual fine-element numbering "i" is omitted for brevity.)

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el}} - \omega_k^2 \mathbf{M}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el}} & -\mathbf{C}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el}} \\ -\omega_k^2 \mathbf{C}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el} T} & \mathbf{H}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el}} - \omega_k^2 \mathbf{Q}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{M(\alpha),m} \\ \mathbf{p}_{M(\alpha),m} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{u el}} \\ \mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{p el}} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (44)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el}}$, $\mathbf{M}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el}}$, $\mathbf{H}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el}}$, $\mathbf{Q}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el}}$, and $\mathbf{C}_{M(\alpha),m}^{\text{el}}$ correspond to the fine-element state matrices mapped onto the coarse element nodes and assume the following form

$$\mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha),m(i)} = {}^\alpha \Phi_H^{u T} \mathbf{K}_{m(i)}^\alpha {}^\alpha \Phi_H^u, \quad (45a)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{M(\alpha),m(i)} = {}^\alpha \Phi_H^{u T} \tilde{\mathbf{M}}_{m(i)}^\alpha {}^\alpha \Phi_H^u, \quad (45b)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{M(\alpha),m(i)} = {}^\alpha \Phi_H^{p T} \mathbf{H}_{m(i)}^\alpha {}^\alpha \Phi_H^p, \quad (45c)$$

$$\mathbf{Q}_{M(\alpha),m(i)} = {}^\alpha \Phi_H^{p T} \mathbf{Q}_{m(i)}^\alpha {}^\alpha \Phi_H^p, \quad (45d)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{M(\alpha),m(i)} = {}^\alpha \Phi_H^{u T} \mathbf{C}_{m(i)}^\alpha {}^\alpha \Phi_H^p. \quad (45e)$$

In Eqs. (44) and (45) the dependence of the state matrices on (ω_k) is omitted for brevity. Finally, the mapped forcing terms are evaluated as

$$\mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha),m(i)}^{\text{u el}} = {}^\alpha \Phi_H^{u T} \mathbf{f}_{m(i)}^{u,\alpha} \quad (46a)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha),m(i)}^{\text{p, el}} = {}^\alpha \Phi_H^{p T} \mathbf{f}_{m(i)}^{p,\alpha}, \quad (46b)$$

for the nodal forces and outflows, respectively.

In principle, the coarse-element governing equations would be expressed in a form analogous to Eq. (43), i.e.,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha)} - \omega_k^2 \mathbf{M}_{M(\alpha)}^{\text{el}} & -\mathbf{C}_{M(\alpha)} \\ -\omega_k^2 \mathbf{C}_{M(\alpha)}^T & \mathbf{H}_{M(\alpha)} - \omega_k^2 \mathbf{Q}_{M(\alpha)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{M(\alpha)} \\ \mathbf{p}_{M(\alpha)} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha)}^{\text{u el}} \\ \mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha)}^{\text{p el}} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (47)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha)}$, $\mathbf{M}_{M(\alpha)}$, $\mathbf{C}_{M(\alpha)}$, $\mathbf{H}_{M(\alpha)}$, and $\mathbf{Q}_{M(\alpha)}$ denote the coarse-element state matrices and $\mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha)}^{\text{u}}$, $\mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha)}^{\text{p}}$ denote the coarse-element load vectors, respectively. Due to the heterogeneous material distribution at the fine scale, explicit expressions for these matrices do not exist. Yet, these can be evaluated on the basis of energy equivalence between the coarse element domain Eqs. (47) and the upscaled fine-element components Eqs. (45)-(46).

Starting from Eq. (47), the elastic deformation energy at the coarse scale may be evaluated according to Eq. (48) as

$$E_{\text{int}}^K = \int_{\mathcal{K}_{M(\alpha)}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_M^T \mathbb{D} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_M \, d\mathcal{K} = \mathbf{u}_{M(\alpha)}^T \mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha)} \mathbf{u}_{M(\alpha)}. \quad (48)$$

Furthermore, the same energy can be additively decomposed to the contributions of its underlying fine-elements, i.e.,

$$E_{\text{int}}^K = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{m el}}^\alpha} \mathbf{u}_{m(i)}^{\alpha T} \mathbf{K}_{m(i)}^\alpha \mathbf{u}_{m(i)}^\alpha = \mathbf{u}_{M(\alpha)}^T \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{m el}}^\alpha} {}^\alpha \left(\Phi_{m(i)}^{u T} \mathbf{K}_{m(i)}^\alpha {}^\alpha \Phi_{m(i)}^u \right) \mathbf{u}_{M(\alpha)}. \quad (49)$$

Equating Eqs. (48) and 49 and using Eq. (45a) results in the derivation of an explicit expression for the upscaled stiffness matrix of the coarse element, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha)} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{m_{el}}^{\alpha}} \mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha),m(i)}. \quad (50)$$

Upscaled expressions for the remaining state matrices and force vectors are derived on a similar manner. These assume the following form

$$\mathbf{M}_{M(\alpha)} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{m_{el}}^{\alpha}} \mathbf{M}_{M(\alpha),m(i)}^{el}, \quad \mathbf{H}_{M(\alpha)} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{m_{el}}^{\alpha}} \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{M(\alpha),m(i)}^{el}, \quad (51a)$$

$$\mathbf{Q}_{M(\alpha)} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{m_{el}}^{\alpha}} \mathbf{Q}_{M(\alpha),m(i)}^{el}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{M(\alpha)} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{m_{el}}^{\alpha}} \mathbf{C}_{M(\alpha),m(i)}^{el}, \quad (51b)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha)}^u = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{m_{el}}^{\alpha}} \mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha),m(i)}^{u\ el}, \quad \mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha)}^p = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{m_{el}}^{\alpha}} \mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha),m(i)}^p. \quad (51c)$$

The local coarse element state matrices and vectors shown in Eqs. (50)-(51) can be assembled over the coarse domain, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{K}_M = \mathbf{A} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n_{M_{el}}} \mathbf{K}_{M(\alpha)}, \quad \mathbf{M}_M = \mathbf{A} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n_{M_{el}}} \mathbf{M}_{M(\alpha)}, \quad \mathbf{H}_M = \mathbf{A} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n_{M_{el}}} \mathbf{H}_{M(\alpha)}, \quad (52a)$$

$$\mathbf{Q}_M = \mathbf{A} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n_{M_{el}}} \mathbf{Q}_{M(\alpha)}, \quad \mathbf{C}_M = \mathbf{A} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n_{M_{el}}} \mathbf{C}_{M(\alpha)}, \quad (52b)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_M^u = \mathbf{A} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n_{M_{el}}} \mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha)}^u, \quad \mathbf{f}_M^p = \mathbf{A} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n_{M_{el}}} \mathbf{f}_{M(\alpha)}^p, \quad (52c)$$

where \mathbf{A} denotes the standard direct-stiffness assembly operator. Hence, the upscaled global governing equations assume the following form

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_M - \omega_k^2 \mathbf{M}_M & -\mathbf{C}_M \\ -\omega_k^2 \mathbf{C}_M^T & \mathbf{H}_M - \omega_k^2 \mathbf{Q}_M \end{bmatrix}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_M} \underbrace{\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_M \\ \mathbf{p}_M \end{Bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{X}_M} = \underbrace{\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_M^u \\ \mathbf{f}_M^p \end{Bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{F}_M}, \quad (53)$$

where the unknown field vectors \mathbf{u}_M and \mathbf{p}_M denote the coarse-nodal displacements and pressures, respectively.

Eqs. (53) are solved at reduced computational cost to obtain coarse-nodal displacements and pressures, \mathbf{u}_M and \mathbf{p}_M at each coarse-node, respectively. The corresponding fine-scale details are now recovered through a downscaling procedure using the micro-macro mapping relations prescribed in Eqs. (24). Further, secondary quantities such as strains and fluxes can be computed for the i th micro-element in the α th coarse-element as follows

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{m(i)}^{\alpha} = \mathbf{B}^{\epsilon} \mathbf{u}_{m(i)}^{\alpha}, \quad \nabla \mathbf{p}_{m(i)}^{\alpha} = \mathbf{B}^{\nabla p} \mathbf{p}_{m(i)}^{\alpha}, \quad (54)$$

where expressions for \mathbf{B}^{ϵ} and $\mathbf{B}^{\nabla p}$ are evaluated in Appendix B.1.

The algorithmic implementation of the multiscale virtual element method vis-a-vis the assembly of the discretized governing equations at the coarse scale is summarized in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Deriving the upscaled vibro-acoustics governing equations.

Result: Global coarse scale state matrices $\mathbf{K}_M, \mathbf{M}_M, \mathbf{H}_M, \mathbf{Q}_M, \mathbf{C}_M$ and load vectors $\mathbf{f}_M^u, \mathbf{f}_M^p$

foreach coarse element α **do**

 Compute multi-scale basis using Algorithm 1;

foreach micro element i in coarse element α **do**

 Upscale micro-element state matrices for the solid, fluid, and coupling phases using Eqs. (45);

 Upscale micro-element nodal forces and outflows using Eqs. (46);

end

 Assemble reduced order coarse element state matrices and corresponding forcing terms using Eqs. (51);

end

Assemble global governing equations Eqs. (53).

Remark 5. The derivations provided in this work are generic and irrespective of the dimensionality of the problem. This is particularly true for the multiscale implementations introduced in Sections 3, 4, and 5. However, within the scope of this work, development has been carried out only for the case of 2D domains. In terms of the multiscale numerical scheme, extension to 3D necessitates the handling of polyhedral rather than polygonal geometries. Hence, the definition of the boundary conditions has to be performed over a surface domain. Although this aspect is not challenging in its regard, it increases the memory requirements and hence proper data management strategies should be put in place. A more involved challenge of the extension to 3D has to do with the physics of the propagating waves and their interactions; this calls for an updated procedure to evaluate acoustics indices, i.e., sound absorption and sound transmission; this should account for all possible wave directions within the domain also considering the general case of excitations at an oblique angle. Such concepts are beyond the scope of this work.

6 | APPLICATIONS

We investigate the convergence, accuracy, and computational efficiency of the proposed multiscale virtual element formulation through three numerical applications. A first order method $k = 1$ is used in all cases. The accuracy is measured by evaluating the following \mathcal{L}_2 error norms, i.e.,

$$\|\mathbf{u}_h - \mathbf{u}_{ex}\|_{\mathcal{L}_2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_{Q_{el}}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{Q_{el}}} \frac{\|\mathbf{u}_{h(i)}^Q(\omega) - \mathbf{u}_{ex(i)}^Q(\omega)\|}{\|\mathbf{u}_{ex(i)}^Q(\omega)\|}}, \quad (55)$$

and

$$\|\mathbf{p}_h - \mathbf{p}_{ex}\|_{\mathcal{L}_2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_{Q_{ex}}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{Q_{ex}}} \frac{\|\mathbf{p}_{h(i)}^Q(\omega) - \mathbf{p}_{ex(i)}^Q(\omega)\|}{\|\mathbf{p}_{ex(i)}^Q(\omega)\|}}, \quad (56)$$

for the displacement and pressure fields, respectively. In Eqs. (55) and (56), $\mathbf{u}_h^Q(\omega)$, $\mathbf{p}_h^Q(\omega)$ and $\mathbf{u}_{ex}^Q(\omega)$, $\mathbf{p}_{ex}^Q(\omega)$ denote the numerically computed and reference displacements and pressures at an excitation frequency ω , respectively. The quantities are interpolated over a query mesh Q with n_{el}^Q elements. The reference solutions \mathbf{u}_{ex}^Q and \mathbf{p}_{ex}^Q are obtained using finely discretized FEM solutions.

To further investigate the ability of the multiscale VEM to resolve sound transmission in heterogeneous poro-elastic domains, specific acoustic indicators, i.e., the Sound Absorption (SAC) and the Sound Transmission Loss (STL) coefficients are provided (see Eq. (C40)). For validation purposes, a reference SAC or STL curve is generated with the finely discretized post-processed FEM results or the semi-analytical Transfer Matrix Method (TMM)⁶⁴. The procedure followed in computing these indicators is provided in Appendix C.

Section 6.1 establishes the convergence properties of the MsVEM for solid and fluid phases at different frequency steps. Section 6.2 demonstrates the ability of the method to deploy complex coarse element shapes to resolve high frequency excitations. Section 6.3 incorporates the Reduced Basis MsVEM to accelerate model reduction in highly heterogeneous porous domains.

6.1 | Convergence behaviour of the MsVEM for vibroacoustics

A melamine foam of dimensions 57 mm \times 57 mm is subjected to plane-wave excitation at normal incidence in Fig. 8. The domain is provided with anechoic termination to simulate a transmission loss problem.

Two types of elements are considered at the coarse scale, i.e., quadrilateral (QUAD) and polygonal (CVT) elements. For each case, four coarse discretizations are examined. These are summarized in Table 4.

Each coarse-element is subsequently meshed at the fine-scale with the same element type. Four fine-scale discretizations are chosen. These are summarized in Table 5.

A very finely discretized FE solution (20,000 Nodes) is treated as the reference. The relative \mathcal{L}_2 error norms in displacements are shown in Fig. 9 for both coarse element types at three distinct frequencies; these correspond to the lower, mid, and higher end of the spectrum.

Figure 7 Process flowchart of the Reduced Basis Multiscale Virtual Element Method.

Figure 8 A square melamine-foam domain of side 57 mm with plane wave excitation at normal incidence and anechoic termination.

Label	No. of Coarse Elements	No. of Coarse Nodes	
		QUAD	CVT
1	120	164	241
2	480	567	959
3	1920	2093	3836
4	7680	8025	9234

Table 4 Coarse scale discretizations for QUAD and CVT meshes.

Label	No. of Fine Elements
RVE-1	1
RVE-2	9
RVE-3	100
RVE-4	2500

Table 5 Number of QUAD/CVT elements contained in each micro-structure.

235 The QUAD and CVT errors at the low frequency, i.e., $f = 775$ Hz are shown in Figs. 9a and 9d, respectively. In both cases, increasing the fine scale discretization improves the accuracy of the solution. However the differences observed between RVE-1 and RVE-4 are minimal. Furthermore, the errors achieved by the method over both meshes are comparable in quantity.

240 Figs. 9b and 9e depict the errors at the mid-range frequency $f = 2700$ Hz. Once again, the errors achieved by both coarse element types are identical. However, there is a noticeable decrease in the overall accuracy when compared to their low frequency counterparts, i.e., Figs. 9a and 9d for the QUAD and CVT meshes, respectively. This is because the $f = 2700$ Hz excitation contains a larger wave number. Hence, a higher resolution is required at the fine scale to achieve the same accuracy.

The same observations hold for the high-frequency cases shown in Figs. 9c and 9f. Both coarse element types result in nearly identical trends although the errors achieved are higher when compared to the mid-range frequency.

245 The relative \mathcal{L}_2 error norms in pressures are provided at the same frequency steps for both meshes in Fig. 10. Once again, similar behaviour is observed across meshes at the same frequency step. Further, the same reduction in accuracy is seen with increasing excitation frequencies.

Figure 9 Convergence of relative errors in displacements as computed by the MsVEM at excitation frequencies 775 Hz, 2700 Hz and 5500 Hz.

The relative \mathcal{L}_2 error norms have a theoretical upper bound

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{u}_h - \mathbf{u}_{ex}\|_{\mathcal{L}_2} &\leq C_u h^{s_u}, \\ \|p_h - p_{ex}\|_{\mathcal{L}_2} &\leq C_p h^{s_p}, \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

where C_u and C_p denote appropriately chosen arbitrary scalar valued constants; h denotes the coarse-element diameter and s_u , s_p indicate the orders of convergence. In this case the theoretical values are $s_u = s_p = 2$. The h^2 reference line is also provided in all figures for comparing the rates of convergence.

250 The magnitude of the numerically obtained rates of convergence for the all RVE choices, **RVE-1** through **RVE-4**, are illustrated at all three frequencies for the displacements in Fig. 11a and for the pressures in Fig. 11b. The convergence rates are evaluated as the slope of the error plots shown in Figs. 9 and 10 for the displacements and pressures, respectively. It is observed in all cases that the choice of microstructure does not significantly affect any convergence rate trends. A slightly reduced average rate of 1.8 is yielded for displacements in the case of QUAD and CVT meshes at $f = 775$ Hz. Optimal or near-optimal rates are noticed in all other cases.

6.2 | Periodically repeating inclusions

260 The case of periodically embedding rigid inclusions within a porous domain with motionless skeleton to improve low frequency absorption behaviour is considered here⁶⁵. The material parameters used are provided in Table 6. The domain is subjected to a plane wave excitation at normal incidence and has a rigid backing support. The MsVEM is applied with the objective of driving down computational costs. Linear kinematical constraints are employed throughout this example to compute the multiscale basis functions. A square unit cell, i.e., a 2 cm \times 2 cm domain with a circular mesoscale inclusion of radius 7.5 mm is selected for the upscaling procedure. This is shown in Fig. 12(I).

265 This coarse element is periodic in the vertical direction with a period of 2 cm. It is discretized with 625 CVT fine elements and comprises 4 coarse nodes. The application of this 4-noded unit cell to this problem on the other hand, only results in 10 coarse elements and 22 coarse DoFs (see "RVE1-0" in Tables 7 and 8).

Figure 10 Convergence of relative errors in pressures at excitation frequencies 775 Hz, 2700 Hz and 5500 Hz.

Figure 11 Comparison of numerically obtained convergence rates from (a) Fig. 9 for the displacements and (b) Fig. 10 for the pressures with their corresponding theoretical rates.

The resulting SAC is labeled "RVE1-0" and shown in Fig. 14a. Although the predicted SAC closely follows the reference solution "ref" up to approximately 3000 Hz, the peak SAC is overestimated and significant deviations are observed for higher frequencies. Furthermore, the predicted response fails to capture the increase in sound absorption for frequencies higher than 6000Hz.

σ	ϕ	α_∞	Λ	Λ'
$\text{N} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{m}^{-4}$	-	-	m	m
8900	0.95	1.42	180×10^{-6}	360×10^{-6}

Table 6 Macroscopic material parameters corresponding to the porous material with rigid motionless skeleton.

Figure 12 Coarse elements examined and proposed as future extensions.

270 As already discussed in Section 6.1, the convergence of the method is not very sensitive to the fine scale discretization that should, in this case, be able to capture the high frequency response of the domain. Rather, the discrepancies should be tracked down to the coarse scale discretization.

275 However, one cannot simply do a classical h-refinement at the coarse scale as is traditionally done. This is because the periodic nature of the underlying domain does not naturally allow for arbitrarily small periodic unit cells. In such cases, one opts for p-refinement inspired strategies instead, analogous to⁶⁰. Using an edge refinement/node insertion strategy, unit cells of the same geometry are generated, having 2, 5 and 10 subdivisions per edge. These correspond to 8, 20 and 40 coarse nodes per unit cell as summarized in Table 7. The SAC curves obtained for the unit cells are represented by curves "RVE1-1", "RVE1-2" and "RVE1-3" in Fig. 14a. Appreciable improvement over the "RVE1-0" is noticed, in ascending order of number of subdivisions per edge. The peak at 3000 Hz is progressively represented more accurately and more realistic behaviour at mid-high frequencies > 6000 Hz is retrieved.

280 The SACs obtained by "RVE1-2" and "RVE1-3" in Fig. 14a are practically equivalent. This reveals that the method has converged for this particular choice of RVE. It is reasonable to assume that no further appreciable improvement in behaviours at frequencies above 6000 Hz can be expected with further edge refinement. The high frequency (10 kHz) downscaled pressure contours associated with "RVE1-3" are shown in Fig. 13b. The contours obtained over a single unit cell are also provided for further clarity. The coarse nodes are denoted in bold. As expected, appreciable deviations are observed when compared with the reference solution provided by the VEM, which is shown in Fig. 13a.

290 To further improve the accuracy, the ability of the method to accommodate flexible, potentially non-convex coarse elements is now exploited. The current square unit cell is split horizontally into two as shown in Fig. 12(II). It is to be noted that here the unit cell shape implicitly accounts for the rigid inclusion. Owing to the prevalence of curved boundaries for these elements, one needs multiple coarse nodes per edge even at a low fidelity setting to faithfully capture the coarse element geometry. The number of coarse nodes per unit cell involved are shown in Table 7 under Labels "RVE2-0", "RVE2-1", "RVE2-2" and "RVE2-3". The associated SAC contours are provided in Fig. 14b.

295 A significant improvement in the SAC computation is observed here. The peak at 3000 Hz is more accurately captured and the high-frequency responses are predicted more realistically. The curves "RVE2-1", "RVE2-2" and "RVE2-3" correctly capture the peak at 3000 Hz and also replicate the increasing trend beyond 6000 Hz. However, the sound absorption is still under-predicted at higher frequencies. The similarities in "RVE2-2" and "RVE2-3" reveal the solutions have converged for this RVE choice. No further improvements in the solution can be reasonably expected with increasing the number of coarse nodes. The pressure

Figure 13 Pressure contours at $f = 10$ kHz.

contour offered by "RVE2-3" at 10 kHz is provided in Fig. 13c. Once again, the deviations from the reference contour (Fig. 13a) are noticeable.

300 To achieve further improvements in accuracy, one seeks to augment the coarse scale discretization even further by splitting the two unit cells vertically to obtain 4 periodically repeating coarse elements. This is illustrated in Fig. 12(III). As before, four fidelity schemes are considered. These are detailed as "RVE3-0", "RVE3-1", "RVE3-2" and "RVE3-3" in Tables 7 and 8. The relevant SACs are shown in Fig. 14c. Here, a near perfect fit with the reference solution is obtained at all frequencies using

Label	Periodic Unit Cells	Type	Coarse Nodes/ unit cell	Fine Elements/ unit cell	Unit Cell Description
RVE1-0	1	I	4	2,500	
RVE1-1	1	I	8	2,500	Convex
RVE1-2	1	I	20	2,500	Quadrilateral
RVE1-3	1	I	40	2,500	
RVE2-0	2	II	40	2,500	
RVE2-1	2	II	112	2,500	Non-Convex
RVE2-2	2	II	190	2,500	Polygon
RVE2-3	2	II	272	2,500	
RVE3-0	4	III	60	2,500	
RVE3-1	4	III	212	2,500	Non-Convex
RVE3-2	4	III	295	2,500	Polygon
RVE3-3	4	III	373	2,500	

Table 7 Unit cell configurations.

Label	Total Coarse Nodes	Total Coarse Elements	Total Fine Nodes	Total Fine Elements
RVE1-0	22	10	49,644	25,000
RVE1-1	53	10	49,644	25,000
RVE1-2	146	10	49,644	25,000
RVE1-3	301	10	49,644	25,000
RVE2-0	333	20	49,644	25,000
RVE2-1	951	20	49,644	25,000
RVE2-2	1601	20	49,644	25,000
RVE2-3	2381	20	49,644	25,000
RVE3-0	493	40	49,644	25,000
RVE3-1	1695	40	49,644	25,000
RVE3-2	2478	40	49,644	25,000
RVE3-3	3194	40	49,644	25,000

Table 8 Global mesh information for the unit cell configurations.

"RVE3-3". The pressure contour at 10 kHz as generated using "RVE3-3" is given in Fig. 13d. The contour is practically identical to Fig. 13a. A speed-up of 2.68 is offered by "RVE3-3" over the full VEM computation.

6.3 | Highly heterogeneous poroelastic domain

Manufacturing limitations can introduce uncertainties in the underlying material configuration of a porous material. Such heterogeneities can play a significant role in affecting its absorption or transmission behaviour. This example investigates the ability of the MsVEM and reduced basis MsVEM to provide accurate and efficient simulations of such materials. A rectangular poroelastic domain is subjected to a plane wave acoustic excitation at normal incidence. The support and boundary conditions are identical to Fig. 8. 100 equally spaced frequency steps are considered within the range [20, 5000] Hz for the excitation. The Young's modulus and static airflow resistivity are treated as random fields. The Young's modulus is sampled from a lognormal distribution with mean $\mu_E = 10^6 N \cdot m^{-2}$ and standard deviation $\text{std}_E = 10^2$. The resistivity is sampled from a similar distribution with mean $\mu_\sigma = 10^5 N \cdot s \cdot m^{-4}$ and standard deviation $\text{std}_\sigma = 10^2$. This example illustrates the performance of the above

Figure 14 Convergence of SAC on the coarse element realisations defined in Table 7.

315 mentioned methods for a single realization. The corresponding fields are respectively shown in Fig. 15. The remaining material parameters are homogeneously distributed and summarized in Table 9.

ϕ	α_∞	Λ	Λ'	ν	η_s	ρ
-	-	m	m	-	-	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$
0.99	1.01	9.8×10^{-5}	1.96×10^{-4}	0.44	0.1	8

Table 9 Homogeneous macroscopic material parameters.

The domain is resolved with two meshes, detailed in Table 10. Mesh A contains 22,500 CVT elements. The multiscale mesh (Mesh B) comprises 100 coarse CVT elements. Each coarse element subsequently clusters 225 fine CVT elements within its interior.

Figure 15 (a) Randomly sampled heterogeneous Young's modulus field, (b) Randomly sampled heterogeneous resistivity.

Full Mesh (Mesh A)		Multiscale Mesh (Mesh B)			
-	-	Macro		Micro	
Elements	Nodes	Elements	Nodes	Elements	Nodes
22500	44918	100	201	225	449

Table 10 Number of elements and nodes contained in each mesh.

Figure 16 Net displacement contours \mathbf{u}_h at 5000 Hz.

320 The displacement contours as evaluated by the VEM over Mesh A and the MsVEM (with oscillatory boundary conditions) over Mesh B are displayed in Figs. 16a and 16b, respectively. The contours as calculated by the Reduced Basis MsVEM (RBMsVEM) are also provided in Fig. 16c. Similarly, the corresponding pressure contours are provided in Fig. 17. A good agreement is observed between all methods.

The Sound Transmission Loss (STL) coefficient obtained across the spectrum is provided in Fig. 18. The STL curve corresponding to the MsVEM and RBMsVEM are observed to be practically identical to the VEM solution.

325 The computational run times incurred at critical bottlenecks by the three methods are provided in Fig. 19. The data provided herein has been averaged over three runs. The total time taken by each method is given in Fig. 19a. This is divided into preprocessing, solving and postprocessing phases. The time taken for different operations in the preprocessing phase is highlighted in Fig. 19b. This comprises entirely of assembling operations for the VEM. The multiscale methods consist of an additional

Figure 17 Pressure contours, i.e., p_h at 5000 Hz.

Figure 18 Sound Transmission Loss coefficient as calculated with the VEM, MsVEM and RBMsVEM for the heterogeneous realization shown in Fig. 15.

330 operation where multiscale basis functions are evaluated. The upscaling procedure is included within the assembly times here. Finally, the time required by the RBMsVEM to calculate the high-fidelity snapshot matrix, perform the SVD and obtain the POD basis is accounted for in the label "POD Basis".

It can be seen from Fig. 19b that the total pre-processing time taken by the MsVEM and RBMsVEM is significantly lower than the VEM. The reduced basis procedure proves to be relatively inexpensive, and noticeably accelerates computation of
335 multiscale bases. The upscaling and assembly procedure costs incurred by both multiscale methods are comparable.

Fig. 19a shows that the spectral solution procedure (more specifically, the iterative frequency domain solution procedure) is the primary bottleneck in fine-scale methods. The cost incurred at this phase by the multiscale methods is nearly negligible (1.46 s and 1.59 s for the MsVEM and RBMsVEM, respectively). The downscaling phase, where fine scale information is retrieved, is comparable in both multiscale methods, as evidenced by the postprocessing times. This operation is non-existent in the VEM,
340 where acoustic indicators can directly be computed after solving.

The MsVEM and RBMsVEM offer speedups of 7.75 and 11.97, respectively, over the VEM solution. Furthermore, the RBMsVEM results in a speedup of 1.55 over the MsVEM. The speedup metric is defined below with respect to the VEM

$$\text{speedup} = \frac{t_{\text{VEM}}}{t_{\text{MS}}}. \quad (58)$$

Figure 19 (a) Total computational time, (b) Time required for preprocessing.

7 | CONCLUDING REMARKS

The Multiscale Virtual Element Method (MsVEM) is established as a novel efficient alternative to the Multiscale Finite Element Method (MsFEM). In Section 3, the VEM is implemented at the fine-scale of the coupled MsFEM for vibro-acoustics to permit versatile meshing capabilities. This allows for coarse-scale polygonal (non-convex) discretizations as well. Oscillatory kinematic constraints are introduced in Section 3.4 as an improvement over traditional linear and periodic constraints - for the purpose of computing multiscale basis functions. Optimal convergence behaviour of the method with respect to different mesh types is observed in Example 6.1. The potential of using complex coarse element shapes to drive down the computational cost in comparison to traditional FEM and MsFEM methods is demonstrated in Example 6.2 for a rigid porous material with infinitely rigid inclusions.

A Parametric Model Order Reduction (pMOR) scheme based on the POD is introduced at the fine scale for the first time in Section 4 to develop a novel Reduced Basis Multiscale Virtual Element Method. This is used to further accelerate multiscale basis function computations for coupled spectral problems in Example 6.3.

The method is presently applied to 2-D domains. Extensions to account for 3-D geometries is a work in progress. Further, the assumption of weak coupling is inherent to the method (manifesting in the decoupled evaluation of phase-specific multiscale bases); this makes it inappropriate for treating strongly coupled problems, e.g., highly resistive materials and scenarios where the pore-fluid is water.

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510 APPENDIX

A CONSTITUTIVE MODELS

The constitutive relations for the solid skeleton are defined assuming linear-elastic behaviour

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s = \tilde{\mathbb{D}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s(\mathbf{u}), \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $\tilde{\mathbb{D}}$ denotes the elastic tensor and comprises the modified Young's modulus $\tilde{\mathbb{E}}$ and the Poisson's ratio ν ,

$$\tilde{\mathbb{D}} \equiv \tilde{\mathbb{D}}(\tilde{\mathbb{E}}, \nu), \quad (\text{A2})$$

and $\tilde{\mathbb{E}}$ is defined as

$$\tilde{\mathbb{E}} = E(1 + j\eta_s(\omega)), \quad (\text{A3})$$

where E and $\eta_s(\omega)$ are the Young's modulus and the structural loss factor, respectively. The complex-valued and frequency dependent nature of a material constant is symbolically represented by $(\tilde{\cdot})$; the symbol j stands for the unit complex number $j = \sqrt{-1}$. The infinitesimal strain operator $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s(\cdot)$ has the form

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T). \quad (\text{A4})$$

The dynamic bulk modulus \tilde{K}_{eq} and the dynamic mass density $\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}}$, respectively capture the thermal and visco-inertial dissipation effects of the pore-fluid. These parameters are obtained through a chosen semi-phenomenological dissipation model, such as the JCA, JCAL and JCPL models. The JCAL model is provided as follows

$$\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}}(\omega) = \frac{\alpha_\infty \rho_0}{\phi} \left[1 + \frac{\sigma \phi}{j \omega \rho_0 \alpha_\infty} \sqrt{1 + j \frac{4 \alpha_\infty^2 \eta \rho_0 \omega}{\sigma^2 \Lambda^2 \phi^2}} \right], \quad (\text{A5a})$$

$$\tilde{K}_{\text{eq}}(\omega) = \frac{\gamma P_0 / \phi}{\gamma - (\gamma - 1)A}, \quad (\text{A5b})$$

where A is equal to

$$A = \left[1 - j \frac{\phi \kappa}{k'_0 C_p \rho_0 \omega} \sqrt{1 + j \frac{4 k_0'^2 C_p \rho_0 \omega}{\kappa \Lambda'^2 \phi^2}} \right]^{-1}. \quad (\text{A6})$$

The macroscopic material parameters α_∞ , σ , η , Λ , Λ' , γ , P_0 , k'_0 , C_p and κ denote the high frequency limit of dynamic tortuosity, static airflow resistivity, dynamic viscosity, viscous and thermal characteristic lengths, adiabatic index, atmospheric pressure, static thermal permeability, specific heat at constant pressure and thermal conductivity. An expansive list of all existing semi-phenomenological models is available in⁶⁶. The modified Biot density $\tilde{\rho}$ is evaluated

$$\tilde{\rho} = \tilde{\rho}_{11} - \frac{\tilde{\rho}_{12}^2}{\tilde{\rho}_{22}}, \quad (\text{A7a})$$

$$\tilde{\rho}_{11} = \rho_1 - \tilde{\rho}_{12}, \quad (\text{A7b})$$

$$\tilde{\rho}_{12} = \phi \rho_0 - \tilde{\rho}_{22}, \quad (\text{A7c})$$

$$\tilde{\rho}_{22} = \phi^2 \tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}}. \quad (\text{A7d})$$

The solid frame density ρ_1 is obtained as $\rho_1 = (1 - \phi)\rho_s$, where ρ_s contains the density of the grain material. The material porosity is represented by ϕ ; ρ_0 represents static air density. The coupling factor $\tilde{\gamma}$ is expressed

$$\tilde{\gamma} = \phi \left(\frac{\tilde{\rho}_{12}}{\tilde{\rho}_{22}} - \frac{\tilde{Q}}{\tilde{R}} \right), \quad (\text{A8})$$

Parameter	Description	Value	Units
σ_s	in-vacuo stress tensor		$N \cdot m^{-2}$
ϵ_s	infinitesimal strain tensor		-
E	Young's modulus		$N \cdot m^{-2}$
ν	Poisson's ratio		-
$\eta_s(\omega)$	structural loss factor		-
\tilde{D}	elastic constitutive tensor		$N \cdot m^{-2}$
$\tilde{\rho}$	modified Biot density		$kg \cdot m^{-3}$
$\tilde{\rho}_{eq}$	dynamic mass density		$kg \cdot m^{-3}$
\tilde{K}_{eq}	dynamic bulk modulus		$N \cdot m^{-2}$
$\tilde{\gamma}$	coupling factor		-
ω	angular frequency		$rad \cdot s^{-1}$
ϕ	porosity		-
ρ_s	solid skeleton-material density		$kg \cdot m^{-3}$
ρ_0	air density at rest	1.2042	$kg \cdot m^{-3}$
ρ_1	solid skeleton-frame density		$kg \cdot m^{-3}$
K_b	porous skeleton bulk modulus at constant pressure		$N \cdot m^{-2}$
K_s	solid skeleton-material bulk modulus		$N \cdot m^{-2}$
K_f	fluid bulk modulus		$N \cdot m^{-2}$
σ	static airflow resistivity		$N \cdot s \cdot m^{-4}$
α_∞	high frequency limit of dynamic tortuosity		-
Λ	viscous characteristic length		m
Λ'	thermal characteristic length		m
k'_0	static thermal permeability		m^2
c_{air}	speed of sound in air	343.377	$m \cdot s^{-1}$
z_{air}	impedance of air	413.4807	$kg \cdot m^{-2} \cdot s^{-1}$
P_0	atmospheric pressure	101,325	$N \cdot m^{-2}$
C_p	specific heat of fluid at constant pressure	1.0024×10^3	$J \cdot kg^{-1}$
η	dynamic viscosity	1.8214×10^{-5}	$N \cdot s \cdot m^{-2}$
γ	adiabatic index	1.4012	-
α	sound absorption coefficient		-
\mathcal{T}	sound transmission loss coefficient		-
κ	thermal conductivity	0.0257	$W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$
k	wave number of acoustic excitation		m^{-1}

Table A1 Material parameters used in the Biot $\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{p}$ formulation.

where the elastic coupling behaviour between both phases is captured by \tilde{Q} . Further, the bulk modulus of a fluid occupying a volume fraction ϕ of the porous media under consideration is contained in \tilde{R} . These are written as follows

$$\tilde{Q} = \frac{\left[1 - \phi - \frac{K_b}{K_s}\right] \phi K_s}{\tilde{D}}, \quad (\text{A9a})$$

$$\tilde{R} = \frac{\phi^2 K_s}{\tilde{D}}, \quad (\text{A9b})$$

$$\tilde{D} = 1 - \phi - \frac{K_b}{K_s} + \phi \frac{K_s}{K_f}, \quad (\text{A9c})$$

where K_b is the bulk modulus of the porous skeleton at constant air pressure, K_s is the grain bulk modulus and K_f is the fluid bulk modulus.

All material parameters involved are provided in Table A1.

515 B IMPLEMENTING THE VEM

B.1 Evaluating VEM projectors

The expressions for \mathbf{K}_m and \mathbf{H}_m in Eqs. (6) and (10) are derived from bilinear forms obtained for the weak formulation of Eq. (1)

$$a_{\mathcal{K}_m}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h, \delta \mathbf{u}_h) = \mathbf{u}_m^T \underbrace{\left[\int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_h^u) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_h^u) d\Omega \right]}_{\mathbf{K}_m} \mathbf{u}_m, \quad (\text{B10})$$

and

$$b_{\mathcal{K}_m}^\nabla(\mathbf{p}_h, \delta \mathbf{p}_h) \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_{\text{eq}}} = \mathbf{p}_m^T \underbrace{\left[\int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_{\text{eq}}} \nabla \boldsymbol{\Phi}_h^p \cdot \nabla \boldsymbol{\Phi}_h^p d\Omega \right]}_{\mathbf{H}_m} \mathbf{p}_m. \quad (\text{B11})$$

The operator specific projectors used in Eq. (13) are defined using energetic orthogonality criteria

$$\begin{cases} \Pi_k^\varepsilon := a_{\mathcal{K}_m}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h - \Pi_k^\varepsilon \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{m}) = 0 \\ \forall \mathbf{u}_h \in \mathcal{V}_h^u, \mathbf{m} \in [\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2 \setminus \mathbb{K}^\varepsilon(\mathcal{K}_m), \end{cases} \quad (\text{B12})$$

and

$$\begin{cases} \Pi_k^{\nabla p} := b_{\mathcal{K}_m}^\nabla(\mathbf{p}_h - \Pi_k^{\nabla p} \mathbf{p}_h, \mathbf{m}) \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_{\text{eq}}} = 0, \\ \forall \mathbf{p}_h \in \mathcal{V}_h^p, \mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m) \setminus \mathbb{K}^\nabla(\mathcal{K}_m), \end{cases} \quad (\text{B13})$$

where \mathbb{M}_k and $\mathbb{K}^{(\cdot)}$ denote monomial spaces and operator-specific kernels.

The contents of the monomial spaces $[\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2$ and $[\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)]$ are iteratively defined in Table B2.

Polynomial order	$\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)$	$[\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2$
$k = 0$	$\mathbb{M}_0(\mathcal{K}_m) = \{1\}$	$[\mathbb{M}_0(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2 = \left\{ \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix} \right\}$
arbitrary order k	$\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}) = \left\{ \mathbb{M}_{k-1}(\mathcal{K}), \begin{matrix} \xi^k \\ \xi^{k-1}\eta \\ \dots \\ \eta^k \end{matrix} \right\}$	$[\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K})]^2 = \left\{ \begin{matrix} [\mathbb{M}_{k-1}(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2, & \begin{Bmatrix} \xi^k \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \\ \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \xi^k \end{Bmatrix}, & \begin{Bmatrix} \xi^{k-1}\eta \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, & \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \xi^{k-1}\eta \end{Bmatrix} \\ \dots & \begin{Bmatrix} \eta^k \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, & \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \eta^k \end{Bmatrix} \end{matrix} \right\}$

Table B2 Generalized scalar and vector valued monomials for $\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)$ and $[\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2$, respectively.

In Table B2, $\xi = \frac{x-x_{\mathcal{K}}}{h_{\mathcal{K}}}$ and $\eta = \frac{y-y_{\mathcal{K}}}{h_{\mathcal{K}}}$ denote scaled monomials in each parametric direction. The number of terms in $[\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2$ and $[\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)]$ are $n_k^u = (k+1)(k+2)$ and $n_k^p = \frac{(k+1)(k+2)}{2}$, respectively. The operator-specific kernels are provided in Table B3. The contents of these kernels can be derived using kinematical decomposition relations mentioned in⁵⁹.

Operator	Label	Contents	Number of Elements
$a_{\mathcal{K}_m}^\varepsilon(\cdot, \cdot)$	$\mathbb{K}^\varepsilon(\mathcal{K}_m)$	$\left\{ \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix}, \begin{Bmatrix} \eta \\ -\xi \end{Bmatrix} \right\}$	3
$a_{\mathcal{K}_m}^\nabla(\cdot, \cdot)$	$\mathbb{K}^{\nabla u}(\mathcal{K}_m)$	$\left\{ \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix} \right\}$	2
$a_{\mathcal{K}_m}^0(\cdot, \cdot)$	$\mathbb{K}^{0u}(\mathcal{K}_m)$	$\{\emptyset\}$	0
$b_{\mathcal{K}_m}^\nabla(\cdot, \cdot)$	$\mathbb{K}^{\nabla p}(\mathcal{K}_m)$	$\{1\}$	1
$b_{\mathcal{K}_m}^0(\cdot, \cdot)$	$\mathbb{K}^{0u}(\mathcal{K}_m)$	$\{\emptyset\}$	0

Table B3 Definition of operator kernels

The polynomial components \mathbf{u}_h^ε and \mathbf{p}_h^ε are expanded in the relevant monomial bases according to Eqs. (B12)-(B13)

$$\Pi_k^\varepsilon \mathbf{u}_h = \sum_{i=1}^{n_k^\varepsilon - 3} \mathbf{m}_{i+3} \zeta_i^\varepsilon \equiv \mathbf{m}^\varepsilon \zeta^\varepsilon, \quad (\text{B14a})$$

$$\Pi_k^{\nabla p} \mathbf{p}_h = \sum_{i=1}^{n_k^{\nabla p} - 1} \mathbf{m}_{i+1} \zeta_i^{\nabla p} \equiv \mathbf{m}^{\nabla p} \zeta^{\nabla p}, \quad (\text{B14b})$$

where ζ_i^ε is a $(1 \times n_{\text{dof}}^\varepsilon)$ vector of the unknown expansion coefficients. Similarly, $\zeta_i^{\nabla p}$ is a $(1 \times n_{\text{dof}}^{\nabla p})$ sized vectors. Eqs. (B14) are inserted into Eqs. (B12) and (B13) and solved for using the following

$$\zeta^\varepsilon = [\mathbf{G}^\varepsilon]^{-1} \mathbf{B}^\varepsilon, \quad (\text{B15a})$$

$$\zeta^{\nabla p} = [\mathbf{G}^{\nabla p}]^{-1} \mathbf{B}^{\nabla p}, \quad (\text{B15b})$$

where ζ^ε and $\zeta^{\nabla p}$ are arrays whose i_{th} rows hold ζ_i^ε and $\zeta_i^{\nabla p}$, respectively. The arrays \mathbf{G}^ε and $\mathbf{G}^{\nabla p}$ read

$$\mathbf{G}_{ij}^\varepsilon = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \varepsilon_s(\mathbf{m}_{i+3})^T \sigma_s(\mathbf{m}_{j+3}) d\mathcal{K}, \quad (\text{B16})$$

and

$$\mathbf{G}_{ij}^{\nabla p} = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} (\nabla \mathbf{m}_{i+1})^T \frac{1}{\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}}} \nabla \mathbf{m}_{j+1} d\mathcal{K}. \quad (\text{B17})$$

The quantities \mathbf{B}^ε and $\mathbf{B}^{\nabla p}$ are arrays whose j_{th} row is a vector

$$\mathbf{B}_j^\varepsilon = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} \varepsilon_s(\mathbf{u}_h)^T \sigma_s(\mathbf{m}_{j+3}) d\mathcal{K}. \quad (\text{B18})$$

and

$$\mathbf{B}_j^{\nabla p} = \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} (\nabla \mathbf{p}_h)^T \frac{1}{\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}}} \nabla \mathbf{m}_{j+1} d\mathcal{K}. \quad (\text{B19})$$

B.2 Evaluating consistency terms

Inserting Eq. (13) into the bilinear terms introduced in Eqs. (B10)-(B11) yields

$$a_{\mathcal{K}_m^\alpha}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h, \delta \mathbf{u}_h) = a_{\mathcal{K}_m^\alpha}^\varepsilon(\Pi_k^\varepsilon \mathbf{u}_h, \Pi_k^\varepsilon \delta \mathbf{u}_h) + a_{\mathcal{K}_m^\alpha}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h - \Pi_k^\varepsilon \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{u}_h - \Pi_k^\varepsilon \delta \mathbf{u}_h), \quad (\text{B20})$$

and

$$a_{\mathcal{K}_m^\alpha}^{\nabla p}(\mathbf{p}_h, \delta \mathbf{p}_h) = a_{\mathcal{K}_m^\alpha}^{\nabla p}(\Pi_k^{\nabla p} \mathbf{p}_h, \Pi_k^{\nabla p} \delta \mathbf{p}_h) + a_{\mathcal{K}_m^\alpha}^{\nabla p}(\mathbf{p}_h - \Pi_k^{\nabla p} \mathbf{p}_h, \mathbf{p}_h - \Pi_k^{\nabla p} \delta \mathbf{p}_h). \quad (\text{B21})$$

The first set of terms on the right side are exactly computable and are called *consistency terms*. Since, explicit definitions for \mathbf{u}_h and \mathbf{p}_h do not exist, one seeks easy-to-evaluate approximations for the second set of terms on the right side - these are called

stability terms. Consequently, the associated state matrices read

$$\mathbf{K}_m \approx \mathbf{K}_{m,C} + \mathbf{K}_{m,S}, \quad (\text{B22})$$

and

$$\mathbf{H}_m \approx \mathbf{H}_{m,C} + \mathbf{H}_{m,S}, \quad (\text{B23})$$

where the consistency matrices $\mathbf{K}_{m,C}^{\text{el},\alpha}$ and $\mathbf{H}_{m,C}^{\text{el},\alpha}$ are

$$\mathbf{K}_{m,C} = \boldsymbol{\zeta}^{\varepsilon T} [\mathbf{G}^{\varepsilon}] \boldsymbol{\zeta}^{\varepsilon}, \quad (\text{B24})$$

and

$$\mathbf{H} = \boldsymbol{\zeta}^{\nabla p T} [\mathbf{G}^{\nabla p}] \boldsymbol{\zeta}^{\nabla p}. \quad (\text{B25})$$

B.3 Evaluating stability terms

Owing to the decomposition in Eq. (13), the consistency terms are described through monomial bases; conversely, the stability terms continue to be known through the canonical bases. To facilitate interaction between the two, it is necessary to express the monomials in terms of the canonical bases

$$\Pi_k^{\varepsilon} \mathbf{u}_h = \mathbf{m}^{\varepsilon} \boldsymbol{\zeta}^{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_h^{\varepsilon T} \mathbf{D}^{\varepsilon} \boldsymbol{\zeta}^{\varepsilon}, \quad (\text{B26a})$$

$$\Pi_k^{\nabla p} \mathbf{p}_h = \mathbf{m}^{\nabla p} \boldsymbol{\zeta}^{\nabla p} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_h^{\nabla p T} \mathbf{D}^{\nabla p} \boldsymbol{\zeta}^{\nabla p}, \quad (\text{B26b})$$

where the matrices \mathbf{D}^{ε} and $\mathbf{D}^{\nabla p}$ contain the monomials evaluated at the VEM DoFs in Table 2.

$$\mathbf{D}^{\varepsilon} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{dof}_1(\mathbf{m}_1) & \dots & \text{dof}_1(\mathbf{m}_{n_k^{\varepsilon}-3}) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \text{dof}_{n_{\text{dof}}^{\varepsilon}}(\mathbf{m}_1) & \dots & \text{dof}_{n_{\text{dof}}^{\varepsilon}}(\mathbf{m}_{n_k^{\varepsilon}-3}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{B27a})$$

$$\forall \mathbf{m} \in [\mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m)]^2 \setminus \mathbb{K}^{\varepsilon}(\mathcal{K}_m),$$

$$\mathbf{D}^{\nabla p} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{dof}_1(\mathbf{m}_1) & \dots & \text{dof}_1(\mathbf{m}_{n_k^{\nabla p}-1}) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \text{dof}_{n_{\text{dof}}^{\nabla p}}(\mathbf{m}_1) & \dots & \text{dof}_{n_{\text{dof}}^{\nabla p}}(\mathbf{m}_{n_k^{\nabla p}-1}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{B27b})$$

$$\forall \mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{M}_k(\mathcal{K}_m) \setminus \mathbb{K}^{\nabla p}(\mathcal{K}_m).$$

$$(\text{B27c})$$

The quantities $\text{dof}_i(\mathbf{m}_j)$ and $\text{dof}_i(m_j)$ are evaluated according to the following expressions (see Table 2), for the solid

$$\begin{cases} \text{dof}_i(\mathbf{m}_j) = \mathbf{m}_j(\mathbf{x}_i), & \forall i \leq 2kN_v, \\ \text{dof}_i(\mathbf{m}_j) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}|} \int_{\mathcal{K}} \mathbf{m}_j \cdot \mathbf{m}_\beta \, d\mathcal{K}, \\ \forall \mathbf{m}_\beta \in [\mathbb{M}_{k-2}(\mathcal{K})]^2, & i > 2kN_v, \end{cases} \quad (\text{B28})$$

and the fluid phase

$$\begin{cases} \text{dof}_i(m_j) = m_j(\mathbf{x}_i), & \forall i \leq kN_v, \\ \text{dof}_i(m_j) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}_m|} \int_{\mathcal{K}_m} m_j \cdot m_\beta \, d\mathcal{K}, \\ \forall m_\beta \in \mathbb{M}_{k-2}(\mathcal{K}_m), & i > kN_v, \end{cases}, \quad (\text{B29})$$

525 respectively.

Since the projectors have been computed solely with non-kernel monomials, similar counterparts for the kernel components are required, i.e., $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_S^{\varepsilon}$ and $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_S^{\nabla p}$; along with the relevant change-of-basis transformation matrices $\mathbf{D}_S^{\varepsilon}$ and $\mathbf{D}_S^{\nabla p}$. These matrices

contain kernel monomials evaluated at all DoFs, similar to Eq. (B27):

$$\mathbf{D}_S^\mathcal{E} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{dof}_1(\mathbf{m}_1) & \dots & \text{dof}_1(\mathbf{m}_3) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \text{dof}_{n_{\text{dof}}^u}(\mathbf{m}_1) & \dots & \text{dof}_{n_{\text{dof}}^u}(\mathbf{m}_3) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \forall \mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{K}^\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{K}_m), \quad (\text{B30a})$$

$$\mathbf{D}_S^{\nabla p} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{dof}_1(\mathbf{m}_1) \\ \vdots \\ \text{dof}_{n_{\text{dof}}^p}(\mathbf{m}_1) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \forall \mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{K}^{\nabla p}(\mathcal{K}_m), \quad (\text{B30b})$$

The quantities $\zeta_S^\mathcal{E}$ and $\zeta_S^{\nabla p}$ are now computed in a straightforward way:

$$\zeta_S^\mathcal{E} = [\mathbf{G}_S^\mathcal{E}]^{-1} \mathbf{B}_S^\mathcal{E}, \quad (\text{B31a})$$

$$\zeta_S^{\nabla p} = [\mathbf{G}_S^{\nabla p}]^{-1} \mathbf{B}_S^{\nabla p}, \quad (\text{B31b})$$

where $\mathbf{G}_S^\mathcal{E} = \mathbf{B}_S^\mathcal{E} \mathbf{D}_S^\mathcal{E}$ and $\mathbf{G}_S^{\nabla p} = \mathbf{B}_S^{\nabla p} \mathbf{D}_S^{\nabla p}$. The terms $\mathbf{B}_S^\mathcal{E}$ and $\mathbf{B}_S^{\nabla p}$ are specially defined using relations derived in^{67,68}:

$$\mathbf{B}_S^\mathcal{E} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/N_v & 0 & 1/N_v & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 1/N_v & 0 & 1/N_v & \dots \\ \eta(\mathbf{x}_1) & -\xi(\mathbf{x}_1) & \eta(\mathbf{x}_2) & -\xi(\mathbf{x}_2) & \dots \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{B32a})$$

$$\mathbf{B}_S^{\nabla p} = [1/N_v \ 1/N_v \ \dots]. \quad (\text{B32b})$$

The complete stability-specific projectors are now obtained in the canonical bases

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{tot}}^\mathcal{E} = \mathbf{D}^\mathcal{E} \zeta^\mathcal{E} + \mathbf{D}_S^\mathcal{E} \zeta_S^\mathcal{E}, \quad (\text{B33a})$$

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{tot}}^{\nabla p} = \mathbf{D}^{\nabla p} \zeta^{\nabla p} + \mathbf{D}_S^{\nabla p} \zeta_S^{\nabla p}. \quad (\text{B33b})$$

Finally the stability state-matrices are provided

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{m,S}^{\text{el},\alpha} = (\mathbb{I}_u - \mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{tot}}^\mathcal{E})^T \beta_K (\mathbb{I}_u - \mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{tot}}^\mathcal{E}), \quad (\text{B34a})$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{m,S}^{\text{el},\alpha} = (\mathbb{I}_p - \mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{tot}}^{\nabla p})^T \beta_H (\mathbb{I}_p - \mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{tot}}^{\nabla p}). \quad (\text{B34b})$$

where \mathbb{I}_u and \mathbb{I}_p are identity matrices of sizes $(n_{\text{dof}}^u \times n_{\text{dof}}^u)$ and $(n_{\text{dof}}^p \times n_{\text{dof}}^p)$. The stabilization parameters β_K and β_H are defined using the D-recipe stabilization (originally proposed in⁶⁹ and adapted to a porous media context in⁴⁶) below

$$\beta_K^G = |\mathcal{K}_m| \frac{\text{tr}(\mathbb{D})}{\text{tr}(\mathbf{D}^\mathcal{E} \mathbf{D}^\mathcal{E})}, \quad \beta_H^G = |\mathcal{K}_m| \frac{1/\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}}}{\text{tr}(\mathbf{D}^{\nabla p} \mathbf{D}^{\nabla p})}. \quad (\text{B35})$$

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The reflection coefficient can be obtained for the incident face of a single element $\Gamma_{hl}^\mathcal{K}$

$$R_{\mathcal{K}}(\omega, \theta) = \frac{Z_{\text{sn}\mathcal{K}}(\omega, \theta) - 1}{Z_{\text{sn}\mathcal{K}}(\omega, \theta) + 1}, \quad (\text{C36})$$

where $Z_{\text{sn}\mathcal{K}}(\omega, \theta)$ denotes the associated surface impedance normalized with respect to air $z(\theta)$

$$Z_{\text{sn}\mathcal{K}}(\omega, \theta) = \left(\frac{p_{\mathcal{K}}^{\text{in}}}{v_{n\mathcal{K}}^{\text{in}}} \right)_{\Gamma_{hl}^\mathcal{K}} / z(\theta), \quad (\text{C37})$$

where $p_{\mathcal{K}}^{\text{in}}$ and $v_{n\mathcal{K}}^{\text{in}}$ denote inlet pressures and normal fluid velocities over $\Gamma_{hl}^\mathcal{K}$. The incident pressures (in contrast to the net inlet pressure) is obtained using the reflection coefficient

$$p_{\mathcal{K}}^{\text{inc}} = \left| \frac{p_{\mathcal{K}}^{\text{in}}}{1 + R_{\mathcal{K}}(\omega, \theta)} \right|_{\Gamma_{hl}^\mathcal{K}}, \quad v_{n\mathcal{K}}^{\text{inc}} = \frac{p_{\mathcal{K}}^{\text{inc}}}{z(\theta)}. \quad (\text{C38})$$

To evaluate the time averaged powers, the relations in Eqs. (C39) are used

$$\mathbb{W}^{\text{in}}(\omega, \theta) = \frac{1}{2} \Re \left(\int_{\Gamma_{hl}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{in}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_n^{\text{in}*} d\Gamma \right) = \frac{1}{2} \Re \left(\sum_i \int_{\Gamma_{hl}^{\mathcal{K}(i)}} \mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{K}(i)}^{\text{in}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{n\mathcal{K}(i)}^{\text{in}*} d\Gamma \right), \quad (\text{C39a})$$

$$\mathbb{W}^{\text{inc}}(\omega, \theta) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Gamma_{hl}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{inc}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_n^{\text{inc}} d\Gamma = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \int_{\Gamma_{hl}^{\mathcal{K}(i)}} \mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{K}(i)}^{\text{inc}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{n\mathcal{K}(i)}^{\text{inc}} d\Gamma, \quad (\text{C39b})$$

$$\mathbb{W}^{\text{ref}}(\omega, \theta) = \mathbb{W}^{\text{inc}}(\omega, \theta) - \mathbb{W}^{\text{in}}(\omega, \theta), \quad (\text{C39c})$$

$$\mathbb{W}^{\text{trans}}(\omega, \theta) = \frac{1}{2} \Re \left(\int_{\Gamma_{ho}} \mathbf{p}^{\text{out}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_n^{\text{out}*} d\Gamma \right) = \frac{1}{2} \Re \left(\sum_i \int_{\Gamma_{ho}^{\mathcal{K}(i)}} \mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{K}(i)}^{\text{out}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{n\mathcal{K}(i)}^{\text{out}*} d\Gamma \right), \quad (\text{C39d})$$

where \mathbb{W}^{in} , \mathbb{W}^{inc} , \mathbb{W}^{ref} and $\mathbb{W}^{\text{trans}}$ are the inlet, incident, reflected and transmitted powers, respectively. The operator $(*)$ represents complex conjugation. $\Re(\cdot)$ extracts real valued data. The fluid pressures and normal fluid velocities $\mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{K}(i)}^{\text{out}}$ and $\mathbf{v}_{n\mathcal{K}(i)}^{\text{out}}$ are computed over an elementary outlet face $\Gamma_{ho}^{\mathcal{K}(i)}$. The Sound Absorption Coefficient (α) and Sound Transmission Loss (\mathcal{T}) are finally expressed for incident angle θ and excitation frequency ω

$$\alpha(\omega, \theta) = 1 - \frac{\mathbb{W}^{\text{ref}}(\omega, \theta)}{\mathbb{W}^{\text{inc}}(\omega, \theta)}, \quad \mathcal{T}(\omega, \theta) = 10 \log \frac{\mathbb{W}^{\text{inc}}(\omega, \theta)}{\mathbb{W}^{\text{trans}}(\omega, \theta)}. \quad (\text{C40})$$

There are of course other ways of computing these coefficients, such as the impedance approach⁷⁰, the two-microphone method^{71,72} and the transfer function method⁷³. The reader is referred to^{74,64} for more detailed derivations regarding the post-processing routines required in structural dynamics and vibro-acoustics of porous media.